

Branch-Aware Diagnostics for Generative Probability Paths

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Abstract

Score-based and flow-based generative models learn a single-valued field returning one velocity or score per state and time. When several branches stay compatible with an intermediate state, the target is *multi-valued* and the field can only return their average; the residual is an irreducible variance floor set by the path and coupling, not by model capacity. We introduce *branch-variance decomposition* (BVD), an exact identity (the law of total covariance) that splits this floor over a discrete branch variable into within-branch local uncertainty and between-branch semantic switching, and reads the between-branch share as a coupling diagnostic computable before any model is trained. The same identity holds on the score side, where the between-branch term equals the Fisher information of the branch posterior. In synthetic settings that separate geometry from meaning, a meaning-aware coupling drives branch disagreement from chance to near zero at only a few percent extra transport cost. On CIFAR-10, an unsupervised clustering recovers the between-branch signal that ground-truth labels give from binary to ten-way splits, once the neighborhood bandwidth scales with the branch count. On a trained Flow-Matching model, a posterior-weighted between-branch spread read from the conditional model predicts the velocity-MSE that per-branch conditioning recovers, matching its shape and its magnitude to within about ten percent; an independent estimate corroborates the shape.

1 Introduction

Modern diffusion and Flow Matching samplers pass through intermediate states that are neither pure noise nor committed data. Across their differences they learn a *single-valued* time-dependent field: a reverse denoising chain in DDPMs [19, 44], a continuous-time score field $s_t(x) = \nabla_x \log p_t(x)$ in score-based SDEs [46] realized deterministically by a probability-flow ODE, and a transport velocity on a designed probability path in Flow Matching [3, 31]. In each case the field returns one vector per state and time. This is restrictive exactly when an intermediate state stays compatible with several semantic branches or source-target paths: the regression target is then multi-valued, and the optimal single-valued field can only return the *posterior average* of those compatible directions (Figure 1). The residual conditional variance is the lowest L^2 error any single-valued field can reach for a given path and coupling, identified on the Flow Matching side as a coupling-dependent velocity-variance floor [13, 17, 53, 55] and fixed by the path and coupling rather than by the SNR schedule.

We characterize the internal structure of this floor. Over a discrete *branch variable* K (a class, mode, or cluster the noisy state could still resolve to), the law of total covariance splits the floor \mathcal{A}_v into within-branch local uncertainty $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$ and between-branch switching $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, so $\mathcal{A}_v = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}} + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, and we read their ratio $R_{\text{switch}} = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}/\mathcal{A}_v$ as a coupling diagnostic. This holds on both the velocity and score sides. On the diffusion side the between-branch term equals

Figure 1: Posterior averaging on both sides. **(a)** In a diffusion mixture, the marginal score near a responsibility boundary (where the posterior over branches is split) is a posterior-weighted average of component scores. **(b)** In Flow Matching with two crossing source-target paths, the optimal single-valued velocity is the conditional mean of incompatible path velocities. The same posterior-averaging mechanism leaves an irreducible regression floor on both sides; the score form and the probability-flow-ODE velocity form coincide up to a schedule factor (Proposition 5).

the Fisher information of the branch posterior with respect to the state (how sharply the posterior over K shifts as the state moves). A branch decomposition (Theorem 3) and a score-Jacobian decomposition (Theorem 4), bridged along the probability-flow ODE (Proposition 5), make this precise.

We name this branch-level reading *branch-variance decomposition* (BVD). Its contribution is to apply this covariance identity over a branch variable and predict when branch ambiguity survives a change of coupling, which we prove and confirm below. Two further conjectures on reflow and guidance (§10) extend the same reading. The branch variable K may be an oracle label used for validation or an unsupervised proxy used in deployment, both of which we test on CIFAR-10 CLIP features.

Figure 2 gives an image-level schematic of the same mechanism: a partially noised CIFAR-10 dog can stay compatible with several semantic continuations (dog, cat, horse) whose directions disagree, so a single-valued field returns only their average.

Established interventions act at different surfaces of the generative pipeline, from training-time loss weighting through path and coupling design to sampling-time guidance (reviewed in §2). Rather than treating these as equivalent, BVD provides a common lens for where posterior ambiguity enters and which surface a given intervention acts on, and explains why posterior ambiguity concentrates in a middle-noise window: branch responsibilities are ambiguous there while the single-valued field must average incompatible directions.

Throughout we vary the source-target coupling and the experimental setting. The couplings range from independent pairing and plain Euclidean optimal transport, through a baseline that pairs by correct label but is otherwise geometrically random, to a transport that adds a semantic-matching cost (up to a hard within-condition limit) and a control that uses only the nuisance geometry; we use them as diagnostic interventions that move the within/between split. The settings

Figure 2: Schematic of branch ambiguity at the image level. As a clean image is noised, at an intermediate time t^* the state stays compatible with several semantic branches whose denoising or transport directions disagree; a single-valued field returns only their average, and the disagreement is the between-branch term A_{between} . Thumbnails are illustrative CIFAR-10 dog/cat/horse candidates.

range from low-dimensional analytic oracles, through a controlled 33-dimensional construction that deliberately decouples geometry from meaning, to real CIFAR-10 features and a trained Flow-Matching model. Each coupling and setting is defined where it is introduced (§7, §9). All code, figures, and reproduction scripts are available at <https://github.com/chifongwong-coder/branch-variance-decomposition>.

Contributions. The velocity-variance floor was previously an opaque scalar to be minimized. BVD turns it into a quantity computable from data at each state and time: a per-region readout of where a single-valued field is most strained, an absolute reference that reads a model’s loss as excess risk against a known floor instead of a baseline estimated from a large held-out set, and a test of whether changing the coupling or conditioning on a branch lowers the error before either is built. The technical contributions behind this readout are as follows.

1. **A branch-level decomposition of the regression floor.** We split the known velocity-variance floor into within-branch local uncertainty and between-branch switching, show the split obeys an exact monotone refinement identity and a controlled approximation bound (Propositions 2, 3), and read the between-branch share R_{switch} as a data-computable diagnostic (§8).
2. **The same decomposition on the diffusion side.** We derive it from the mixture-score Jacobian and show its between-branch term is exactly the Fisher information of the branch posterior with respect to the state (Theorem 4 and its corollaries), the score-side counterpart of the velocity between-branch term, the two coinciding up to a schedule factor for the Flow Matching construction matched to the probability-flow ODE (Proposition 5).
3. **Predictions about source-target couplings, proved and tested.** We predict when changing the coupling removes branch ambiguity and when it cannot. Correct labels alone are not enough, and a coupling blind to an external condition can never recover it. Even so, a condition-blind Euclidean coupling aligns a weak semantic coordinate and lowers the semantic ambiguity through it. These are proved as closed-form statements (Propositions 9, 11, 10, 12), realized as Prediction 1 and the three-part Prediction 2 in §9.5, and confirmed in a controlled

experiment that separates geometry from meaning, where a meaning-aware coupling recovers the hidden condition at a few percent extra transport cost (§9.2).

4. **Label-free recovery and a conditioning payoff on real data.** On CIFAR-10 an unsupervised proxy recovers the branch signal that ground-truth labels give across $K=2, 3$, and 10 splits, matching it at $K=2$ and slightly exceeding it at finer K (recovery 0.997 to 1.066, model-free audit), when the neighborhood bandwidth scales with the branch count (§9.3), and on a trained Flow-Matching model the decomposition predicts the velocity-MSE that per-branch conditioning recovers, matching it across three couplings in profile (cosine 0.9998 to 0.9999) and, through a posterior-weighted estimate read from that conditional model, in magnitude to within about ten percent (§9.4; identity $\mathcal{A}_v - \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}} = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, Proposition 1).

2 Related Work

Score matching and diffusion models. Score matching estimates unnormalized densities without computing partition functions [20]. Denoising score matching connects score estimation to denoising corrupted samples [9, 37, 50], whose second-order analogue identifies the score Jacobian with the posterior covariance of the clean signal [21, 36], with an information-theoretic counterpart relating mutual information to mean-square error [12, 26]. DDPMs scaled this principle with a discrete Gaussian Markov chain and a noise-prediction objective [19]. Score-SDEs [46] unified DDPM-like and score-matching methods with continuous-time SDEs, reverse-time SDEs, and probability-flow ODEs. DDIM and ODE solvers emphasize deterministic sampling and numerical integration choices [34, 45].

SNR, critical windows, and semantic commitment. VDM [24] showed that diffusion objectives can be written compactly in terms of SNR. EDM [22] clarified noise-level parameterization, preconditioning, and loss weighting. Min-SNR weighting [16] interprets diffusion training as multi-task learning over timesteps; related work studies negative transfer across noise levels [11]. Limited-interval guidance [28] is most useful in middle noise regimes. Critical-window theory [29] analyzes feature emergence in narrow time intervals, while entropy-based analyses [15] detect the transition from semantic ambiguity to class commitment. Statistical-physics analyses derive sharper phase structure: in mixture-data settings a speciation transition (when modes become distinguishable) precedes a collapse transition (when samples become memorized) [5], with closely related symmetry-breaking and hierarchical-feature transitions [4, 42]. Our diffusion oracle localizes this same regime and links it to the Flow Matching velocity-variance floor.

Flow Matching, OT couplings, and Rectified Flow. Flow Matching (FM) [31] trains CNFs through simulation-free vector-field regression over chosen conditional paths. OT-CFM [49] and multisample Flow Matching [38] show that non-trivial couplings can reduce gradient variance and straighten flows. Rectified Flow and reflow [32] seek straighter ODE trajectories. Stochastic interpolants [3] unify flows and diffusions and allow controlled stochasticity. The qualitative idea that better couplings reduce path crossing is implicit in these works; we instead identify which component of the variance a coupling change moves.

Conditional and semantic transport. Condition-aware transport has been studied directly as a coupling design problem. Classifier-free guidance [18] manipulates conditional and unconditional scores or velocities at sampling time [56]. Stochastic interpolants admit data-dependent couplings that make the source distribution conditional on the target, enabling tasks such as super-resolution and inpainting under the same square-loss objective [2]. Diffusion Schrödinger Bridge Matching iteratively refines the coupling toward an entropy-regularized OT solution [43]. Neural OT and GENOT-like approaches consider flexible cost functions, entropic couplings, and transport across spaces [25]. Closest to our semantic-cost coupling, Cheng and Schwing [7] introduce C²OT, which adds a condition-mismatch term to the minibatch OT cost matrix to address a train-test prior-skew problem in conditional sampling; we use an algebraically similar penalty, swept as a diagnostic of the velocity-ambiguity floor. Triangular conditional optimal-transport flows construct simulation-free maps that couple source to target conditionally on an external variable [23]; the hard-conditional case coincides with the hard-blocked limit of our semantic-cost coupling.

Velocity variance and coupling ambiguity. Several recent works study velocity ambiguity in FM from perspectives closely related to ours. Variational rectified flow matching [13] observes that ground-truth velocity targets at the same intermediate location can point in different directions and that standard MSE training averages these directions, responding by enriching the model class with a structured variational posterior. Hierarchical rectified flow [55] tackles the same multi-valued random-velocity issue by replacing the single ODE with a hierarchy of ODEs. In both cases they enrich the model class to represent the multi-valued structure; we instead keep the model single-valued and decompose the floor.

The coupling-variance perspective [17] identifies a coupling-variance term in the FM loss and shows empirically (on CIFAR-10, CelebA-HQ, and FFHQ) that coupling choices have a large effect on training loss and sample quality, especially in the time-blind setting; the complementary velocity-variance perspective [53] characterizes high- and low-variance regimes of conditional velocities along the noise schedule and proposes variance-reduction training and sampling methods. The scalar quantity we denote $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ aligns with this coupling-variance / velocity-variance floor. Relative to both, which treat that floor as a scalar to act on through method design (variance-reduction training and sampling, or making time conditioning optional under favorable data geometry), the object we study is the partition-relative within/between split of the same floor over a branch variable: we read its between-branch share as a coupling diagnostic and as the reachable conditioning gain $\mathcal{A}_v - \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}} = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$. Concurrent work has applied related variance decompositions in different settings, notably to coreset-induced surrogate sources [52] and to first-moment sub-mode averaging [30], pursuing variance-bounding or sub-mode conditioning rather than coupling diagnosis. Stoica et al. [48] use between-conditional flow dissimilarity as a contrastive *training objective*, whereas we use the between-branch covariance as a *diagnostic* of the same floor.

3 Background and Notation

This section fixes the probability-path notation, the diffusion signal-to-noise parameterization, and the Flow Matching parameterization used throughout the paper.

3.1 Probability paths and vector fields

All random variables in this paper live on a common probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ with values in the Polish state space \mathbb{R}^d (or a finite branch set for K), so that regular conditional probabilities and conditional expectations of the form $\mathbb{E}[\cdot | Y_t = y, T = t]$ exist and are unique up to $P_{Y_t, T}$ -null sets; we use this disintegration convention throughout.

Let p_0 be a simple source distribution and p_1 a target data distribution on \mathbb{R}^d . A probability path is a family $(p_t)_{t \in [0, 1]}$ with endpoints p_0 and p_1 . A deterministic velocity field v_t transports the density by

$$\partial_t p_t(x) + \nabla \cdot (p_t(x)v_t(x)) = 0. \quad (1)$$

A stochastic process may instead satisfy a Fokker-Planck equation. In score-based diffusion, a forward SDE corrupts data and the reverse-time SDE depends on the score $s_t(x) = \nabla_x \log p_t(x)$. Its probability-flow ODE has the same marginals and can be written in velocity-field form.

3.2 Diffusion parameterization and SNR

A common noising model is

$$x_t = \alpha_t x_0 + \sigma_t \varepsilon, \quad \varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I). \quad (2)$$

Under unit data variance, the signal-to-noise ratio is

$$\text{SNR}(t) = \frac{\alpha_t^2}{\sigma_t^2}. \quad (3)$$

Low SNR means the observation carries little information about x_0 ; high SNR means it is close to clean data. In Gaussian diffusion, branch uncertainty therefore resolves in a low-to-mid SNR *commitment window* between these regimes, made precise on the score side in §6.2.

3.3 Flow Matching parameterization

Flow Matching chooses a conditional path between $Z \sim p_0$ and $X \sim p_1$. The simplest path is

$$Y_t = (1 - t)Z + tX, \quad U_t = \partial_t Y_t = X - Z. \quad (4)$$

More generally $Y_t = \psi_t(Z, X)$ and $U_t = \partial_t \psi_t(Z, X)$. A model $v_\theta(y, t)$ is trained by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{FM}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E} \|v_\theta(Y_T, T) - U_T\|^2, \quad (5)$$

where $T \sim \text{Unif}[0, 1]$ unless otherwise specified. Here the *coupling* $\pi(Z, X)$ is the joint distribution from which source-target pairs are drawn during training (independent in vanilla CFM, $Z \perp X$; chosen differently by OT-CFM and condition-aware variants), and the *interpolant* ψ_t is the family of intermediate states (here the straight-line homotopy). Together they determine the intermediate distributions and the ambiguity of the regression target. We use this linear interpolant throughout unless noted otherwise; for a general ψ_t the path velocity is $U_t = \partial_t \psi_t(Z, X)$, and every \mathcal{A}_v / $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$ / $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ / R_{switch} definition carries through with this substitution. Appendix H situates the linear interpolant in the broader DDPM-to-Flow-Matching design-space picture.

4 Branch Ambiguity and Diagnostics

A single-valued generative field returns one velocity or score per state and time, so wherever an intermediate state stays compatible with several branches it can only return their posterior average, and the residual is an irreducible floor. This averaging takes two forms: the conditional mean of path velocities in FM and the posterior-weighted average of component scores in diffusion. This section sets up both, together with the branch variable and the diagnostics; §5 and §6 then decompose the velocity floor and the score Jacobian in turn.

In FM, training examples are source-target pairs $(Z, X) \sim \pi$ and the regression target at intermediate time t is the path velocity $U_t = \partial_t \psi_t(Z, X)$, which under the linear interpolant simplifies to $U = X - Z$. *Branch ambiguity* is the situation where an intermediate state Y_t is statistically compatible with two or more such pairs, and hence with two or more distinct destinations; the wider the set of alternatives the field must average, the larger the residual variance no single-valued field can represent.

Definition 1 (Branch variable). Let $K \in \mathcal{K}$ be a latent branch variable on a finite branch set $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|\}$, so K takes one of $|\mathcal{K}|$ values. In images, K may represent class, layout, pose, style, or a cluster in a representation; for a known mixture distribution, K is the mixture-component index. Writing X_t for the time- t intermediate state (X_t on the diffusion side, the interpolant Y_t on the Flow Matching side, used interchangeably as the conditioning state), a distribution path has branch posterior

$$r_k(x, t) = \mathbb{P}(K = k \mid X_t = x). \quad (6)$$

We use *branch* in the mixture-component sense (one discrete latent index per data sample, in the spirit of mixture-of-experts conditioning), not in the trajectory-level *speciation* sense of the statistical-physics literature and not as the simplex-categorical mode of categorical / discrete flow matching [6, 8].

Assumption 1 (Idealized branch variable). Throughout, K is treated as an idealized branch variable: the analyses assume access to the oracle posterior $r_k(x, t)$. The branch variable is a user-chosen partition (e.g., class labels, k -means clusters, attribute groupings, or an explicit conditioning input), so the diagnostic is partition-relative, defined for the chosen partition. In practice K is approximated by an explicit conditioning input or by a learned representation, and the proxy diagnostics relate to the oracle quantities through the coarsening bound (Proposition 2) and the posterior-stability bound (Proposition 3). A later controlled experiment (§9.2) quantifies what happens when an externally supplied condition only weakly aligns with the practitioner-relevant semantics.

Definition 2 (Branch ambiguity window and diagnostics). A time interval $I \subset [0, 1]$ is a branch ambiguity window if intermediate states in I have high branch posterior entropy or high conditional velocity variance. For diffusion-like paths we use the branch entropy diagnostic

$$H_K(t) = H(K \mid X_t). \quad (7)$$

For Flow Matching paths, with a branch variable K where applicable, we use

$$\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr Cov}(U \mid Y, T = t), \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr} \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(U \mid Y, K, T = t) \mid Y, T = t], \quad (9)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr Cov}(\mathbb{E}[U \mid Y, K, T = t] \mid Y, T = t), \quad (10)$$

$$R_{\text{switch}}(t) = \frac{\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)}{\mathcal{A}_v(t) + \epsilon_0}, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ is the scalar conditional-velocity-variance floor, the same object as the coupling-variance / velocity-variance terms in the variance-perspective FM literature, while $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, R_{switch} are this paper's branch-decomposed components, with their additivity $\mathcal{A}_v = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}} + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ established in Theorem 3. Each component is nonnegative as the trace of a conditional covariance, and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}} \leq \mathcal{A}_v$; with the numerical stabilizer $\epsilon_0 > 0$ this gives $0 \leq R_{\text{switch}}(t) < 1$. Expectations are taken at fixed $T = t$ with the substitution $Y = Y_t$ throughout. For a designated coordinate subset S , with U_S the projection of U onto S (later instantiated as the low-dimensional semantic subspace of the target in §9.2), and an external condition C attached to the source (the branch its paired target should carry, defined in §7), define

$$\mathcal{A}_v^S(t | C) = \mathbb{E}_{Y,C} \text{Tr Cov}(U_S | Y, C, T = t). \quad (12)$$

Although only the S -projection U_S is evaluated, the conditioning variable is the full intermediate state Y , not its projection onto S . We also report normalized ambiguity $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v(t) = \mathcal{A}_v(t) / (\mathbb{E}\|U\|^2 + \epsilon_0)$, whose complement is the explained-variance ratio $R_v^2(t) := 1 - \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v(t)$ (so $1 - R_v^2(t) = \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v(t)$), and its semantic-subspace counterpart

$$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t | C) = \mathcal{A}_v^S(t | C) / (\mathbb{E}\|U_S\|^2 + \epsilon_0), \quad (13)$$

where the denominator expectation is taken over the same paired paths used in the numerator. When the conditioning is balanced and symmetric, the unconditional denominator $\mathbb{E}\|U_S\|^2$ and the C -conditioned denominator $\mathbb{E}[\|U_S\|^2 | C]$ coincide.

The optimal single-valued field is a posterior average, and its residual is the floor we will decompose. The standard projection identity fixes notation and names that floor; here T is the random training time and (Y_T, U_T) the interpolant state and velocity at T , with Y_t, U_t denoting their values at a fixed t .

Theorem 1 (CFM marginalization identity). *Let (Y_T, U_T, T) be jointly defined on a probability space with $T \in [0, 1]$ and $U_T \in L^2$. Among all $v \in L^2(P_{Y_T, T}; \mathbb{R}^d)$, the minimizer of*

$$\mathcal{R}(v) = \mathbb{E}\|v(Y_T, T) - U_T\|^2 \quad (14)$$

is

$$v^*(y, t) = \mathbb{E}[U_T | Y_T = y, T = t] \quad (15)$$

for $P_{Y_T, T}$ -almost every (y, t) , where $P_{Y_T, T}$ is the joint law of (Y_T, T) .

Proof. For any measurable v , condition on (Y_T, T) :

$$\mathbb{E}[\|v(Y_T, T) - U_T\|^2 | Y_T, T] = \|v(Y_T, T) - \mathbb{E}[U_T | Y_T, T]\|^2 \quad (16)$$

$$+ \mathbb{E}[\|U_T - \mathbb{E}[U_T | Y_T, T]\|^2 | Y_T, T]. \quad (17)$$

The second term is independent of v and the first is minimized pointwise by $v = v^*$; v^* is itself a measurable element of $L^2(P_{Y_T, T}; \mathbb{R}^d)$ as the conditional expectation under the disintegration convention of §3, so the pointwise minimizer is admissible. \square

Corollary 1 (Conditional-velocity-variance floor). *The minimum population risk is*

$$\inf_v \mathcal{R}(v) = \mathbb{E}_{Y_T, T} \text{Tr Cov}(U_T | Y_T, T) = \int_0^1 \mathcal{A}_v(t) dt, \quad (18)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr Cov}(U \mid Y_t, T=t)$ is the per- t floor of Definition 2 and the outer $T \sim \text{Unif}[0, 1]$ is the training-time distribution. Thus the conditional velocity variance is the lowest achievable population MSE among all single-valued velocity fields for the chosen path and coupling, and the per- t object $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ is the integrand of this scalar floor. We use it as the starting point for branch-variance decomposition below.

Remark 1 (Coupling-conditional irreducibility). The infimum in Corollary 1 is taken over all measurable single-valued v , with the joint (Y_T, U_T, T) held fixed. The floor therefore depends on the source-target coupling and the interpolant: varying these changes the joint and can lower (or raise) the floor. Our experiments (Section 9) exploit this dependence by holding the marginals fixed while changing the coupling.

We now make the score side precise. For a branch mixture, the marginal score is the posterior-weighted average of the component scores, the score-field counterpart of Theorem 1.

Assumption 2 (Mixture path). For each time t , assume

$$p_t(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} \pi_k p_{t,k}(x), \quad (19)$$

where $\pi_k > 0$, $\sum_k \pi_k = 1$, and each $p_{t,k}$ is C^2 and positive on $\{p_t > 0\}$, with score $s_{t,k}(x) = \nabla_x \log p_{t,k}(x)$. The C^2 regularity is needed for the score-Jacobian decomposition (Theorem 4); Theorem 2 requires only C^1 .

Theorem 2 (Mixture score averaging). *The marginal score $s_t(x) = \nabla_x \log p_t(x)$ is*

$$s_t(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} r_k(x, t) s_{t,k}(x), \quad (20)$$

where

$$r_k(x, t) = \frac{\pi_k p_{t,k}(x)}{\sum_j \pi_j p_{t,j}(x)} = \mathbb{P}(K = k \mid X_t = x). \quad (21)$$

Proof. Differentiate $p_t(x) = \sum_k \pi_k p_{t,k}(x)$:

$$\nabla p_t(x) = \sum_k \pi_k \nabla p_{t,k}(x) = \sum_k \pi_k p_{t,k}(x) s_{t,k}(x). \quad (22)$$

Divide by $p_t(x)$. □

5 Branch-Variance Decomposition in Flow Matching

The scalar floor of Corollary 1 alone cannot distinguish local within-branch uncertainty from semantic switching between branches. To expose this structure, we apply the law of total covariance to the floor conditionally on the branch variable K of Definition 1. This decomposition (BVD) is the main object of the present paper.

Theorem 3 (Branch decomposition of velocity ambiguity). *Let K be a discrete branch variable. For fixed t , let $Y = Y_t$ and $U = U_t \in L^2$. Then*

$$\text{Cov}(U \mid Y, T = t) = \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(U \mid Y, K, T = t) \mid Y, T = t] + \text{Cov}(\mathbb{E}[U \mid Y, K, T = t] \mid Y, T = t). \quad (23)$$

Taking traces and averaging over Y gives

$$\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t). \quad (24)$$

Proof. By the law of total covariance (Eve’s law), for any second-moment random vector U and any sub- σ -algebra \mathcal{G} ,

$$\text{Cov}(U) = \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(U \mid \mathcal{G})] + \text{Cov}(\mathbb{E}[U \mid \mathcal{G}]).$$

Apply this with $U = U_t$ and $\mathcal{G} = \sigma(K)$ conditionally on $(Y, T = t)$. Taking traces and expectation over Y gives the stated decomposition. \square

Remark 2 (Interpretation). $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$ is the ambiguity that remains even after branch identity is known, whereas $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ is the part caused by uncertainty over branch identity. Only the latter is directly tied to semantic switching, and only it can be lowered by coupling interventions that reduce branch overlap in Y_t .

Proposition 1 (Branch-conditioning gain). *Fix t . The population-optimal single-valued field $v^*(y, t) = \mathbb{E}[U \mid Y_t = y]$ and the population-optimal K -conditional field $v_K^*(y, t, k) = \mathbb{E}[U \mid Y_t = y, K = k]$ have irreducible regression risks*

$$\inf_v \mathbb{E}\|U - v(Y_t, t)\|^2 = \mathcal{A}_v(t), \quad \inf_{v_K} \mathbb{E}\|U - v_K(Y_t, t, K)\|^2 = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t),$$

so the risk reduction obtained by conditioning the velocity on the branch variable K is exactly the between-branch ambiguity:

$$\mathcal{A}_v(t) - \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t).$$

Proof. The L^2 minimizer of $\mathbb{E}\|U - v(Y_t, t)\|^2$ is the conditional mean $\mathbb{E}[U \mid Y_t]$, with residual $\mathbb{E}_{Y_t} \text{Tr Cov}(U \mid Y_t) = \mathcal{A}_v(t)$; the minimizer over K -conditional fields is $\mathbb{E}[U \mid Y_t, K]$, with residual $\mathbb{E}_{Y_t, K} \text{Tr Cov}(U \mid Y_t, K) = \mathbb{E}_{Y_t} \text{Tr} \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(U \mid Y_t, K) \mid Y_t] = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$ by the tower rule and the definition of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$. The difference is $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ by Theorem 3. \square

Remark 3 (Operational reading and finite-model form). Proposition 1 gives $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ a decision-value reading: it is the velocity-MSE a practitioner recovers by replacing one shared field with a per-branch field (a class-conditional or mixture-of-experts velocity head). For trained finite-capacity models the measured gain also carries the two models’ excess risks,

$$\text{MSE}_{\text{uncond}}(t) - \text{MSE}_{\text{cond}}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) + (\varepsilon_u(t) - \varepsilon_c(t)),$$

so the realized cross-model gain can deviate from $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ wherever the two suboptimality differ. We test this identity on a trained CIFAR Flow-Matching model (§9.4).

Proposition 2 (Branch refinement monotonicity). (proof in A.1) *Assume $U_t \in L^2$. Let K, K' be two discrete branch variables (finite-valued) with $K = f(K')$ for some deterministic map f (so K' refines K); write $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^K, \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K, R_{\text{switch}}^K$ for the within-branch, between-branch, and switching components of Definition 2 computed with branch variable K , and likewise for K' . Then for each fixed t ,*

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K(t) + \Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t), \quad \Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t) \geq 0, \quad (25)$$

where

$$\Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t) := \mathbb{E}_Y \operatorname{Tr} \mathbb{E}[\operatorname{Cov}(\mathbb{E}[U | Y, K'] | Y, K) | Y] \geq 0. \quad (26)$$

The same nonnegative term is subtracted from the within-branch component,

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^{K'}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^K(t) - \Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t), \quad (27)$$

so that the total $\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^K(t) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^{K'}(t) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'}(t)$ is unchanged. Consequently $R_{\text{switch}}^{K'}(t) \geq R_{\text{switch}}^K(t)$ (with the same ϵ_0 stabilizer).

Remark 4 (Coarse proxy hides between-branch switching). Proposition 2 formalizes the oracle/proxy caveat (Assumption 1 and §8): if a proxy branch variable is a coarsening of an oracle branch variable, the measured $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ and R_{switch} are lower bounds on the oracle quantities; refining the branch labels weakly increases both, while leaving $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ unchanged. For non-nested proxies (e.g., a noisy classifier or arbitrary clustering) monotonicity need not hold, so proxy quality (classifier accuracy, NMI, ARI, posterior L^1 /KL gap) must be reported alongside the diagnostic.

Proposition 3 (Proxy-posterior L^1 stability of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$). (proof in A.2) Fix t and a single discrete branch variable K with finite branch set $\{1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|\}$, and let $m_k(y) := \mathbb{E}[U | Y = y, K = k]$. Let $r(y) = (r_k(y))_k$ and $\hat{r}(y) = (\hat{r}_k(y))_k$ be two probability vectors on this same simplex, with the same first-moment functions $m_k(y)$ used on both sides (so only the weighting distribution differs). Define $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^q(t) := \mathbb{E}_Y \operatorname{Tr} \operatorname{Cov}_{K \sim q(Y)}(m_K(Y))$ and the pointwise Chebyshev radius of the component set,

$$R(y) := \inf_{c \in \mathbb{R}^d} \max_k \|m_k(y) - c\|,$$

i.e., the radius of the smallest enclosing ball of $\{m_k(y)\}_k$. Assume $\bar{R} := \operatorname{ess\,sup}_y R(y) < \infty$. Then

$$|\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^r(t) - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\hat{r}}(t)| \leq 3 \mathbb{E}_Y [R(Y)^2 \|r(Y) - \hat{r}(Y)\|_1] \leq 3\bar{R}^2 \mathbb{E}_Y \|r(Y) - \hat{r}(Y)\|_1. \quad (28)$$

If in addition $\|m_k(y)\| \leq M$ uniformly, then $R(y) \leq M$ pointwise and the loosest form $|\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^r(t) - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\hat{r}}(t)| \leq 3M^2 \mathbb{E}_Y \|r(Y) - \hat{r}(Y)\|_1$ follows. The bound controls sensitivity of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ to the posterior weights on a fixed aligned branch partition; partition misspecification and the replacement of m_k by proxy first moments \hat{m}_k are separate effects.

Remark 5 (Why the Chebyshev form is informative). The tightening $\bar{R} \leq M$ is strict whenever the components $\{m_k(y)\}_k$ are clustered far from the origin: the global- M form charges the absolute magnitude of the first moments, while the R -form charges only their intrinsic spread. This gap is largest in the noise-dominated regime, where the local first moments inherit a large anchor-specific translation from the source component of Y_t , so $R(y) \ll \max_k \|m_k(y)\|$ and the R -form is substantially tighter; Appendix G reports the gap on CIFAR-10 CLIP features. For computation we use the centroid radius $\hat{R}_i^2 := \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}_i} \|m_{i,k} - \bar{m}_i\|^2$, where \mathcal{K}_i is the set of branches present at anchor i , with $\bar{m}_i := |\mathcal{K}_i|^{-1} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_i} m_{i,k}$. Because \bar{m}_i is one admissible choice of the centering $c(y)$ in the proof (Appendix A), $\hat{R}_i^2 \geq R(Y)^2$, so $3\hat{R}_i^2$ is a valid (conservative) bound.

Remark 6 (Relation to $\sqrt{\text{KL}}$ guidance bounds). A guidance-vector analogue with $\sqrt{\text{KL}}$ scaling has been derived for classifier-guided diffusion by Sahu et al. [40]. Pinsker's inequality gives $\|r(y) - \hat{r}(y)\|_1 \leq \sqrt{2 \text{KL}(r(y) \| \hat{r}(y))}$ pointwise in y , so by Jensen $\mathbb{E}_Y \|r(Y) - \hat{r}(Y)\|_1 \leq \sqrt{2 \mathbb{E}_Y \text{KL}(r(Y) \| \hat{r}(Y))}$. The L^1 bound in Proposition 3 keeps the dependence on $\mathbb{E}_Y \|r - \hat{r}\|_1$ explicit rather than substituting this Pinsker upper bound, which would loosen the result whenever the average L^1 deviation is below the Pinsker envelope.

Finite path crossing. Exact crossing points in continuous distributions can be measure-zero. We therefore formalize path crossing through a finite path mixture or a local neighborhood.

Proposition 4 (Local velocity averaging in a finite path mixture). *Let I be a discrete path index with probabilities ρ_i , and define $u_i(t) := \mathbb{E}[U_t \mid I = i, Y_t \in B]$ as the path-conditional mean velocity over the neighborhood $B \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ with $\mathbb{P}(Y_t \in B) > 0$. The local optimal constant velocity over B is*

$$\bar{u}_B(t) = \mathbb{E}[U_t \mid Y_t \in B] = \sum_i \omega_i(B, t) u_i(t), \quad (29)$$

where $\omega_i(B, t) = \mathbb{P}(I = i \mid Y_t \in B)$. The local irreducible L^2 error of any constant velocity over B is $\text{Tr Cov}(U_t \mid Y_t \in B)$, by orthogonal projection onto the velocities constant on B , whose optimum is $\bar{u}_B(t)$.

Proof. The expression for $\bar{u}_B(t)$ is the tower rule conditioned on $\{Y_t \in B\}$; the floor follows from Corollary 1 restricted to vector fields constant on B . \square

6 Mixture Scores and Responsibility-Switching Curvature

The mixture-score averaging of Theorem 2 is the score-side posterior average, weighted by the branch responsibilities r_k (the branch posterior of Definition 1); we now differentiate it. On the velocity side the branch structure shows up in the conditional covariance. The same structure reappears on the score side as an extra curvature term in the score Jacobian, which the following decomposition (the diffusion side of BVD) makes explicit and quantitative.

6.1 Score Jacobian and switching curvature

Theorem 4 (Score Jacobian decomposition). (proof in A.3) *Adopt Assumption 2, with a finite branch set $|\mathcal{K}| < \infty$ (so that the product rule applies termwise to the finite sum $s_t = \sum_k r_k s_{t,k}$, using C^1 regularity of r_k and $s_{t,k}$ on $\mathcal{X}_t := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : p_t(x) > 0\}$ from Assumption 2). Let $Ds_t(x)$ denote the Jacobian. Then on \mathcal{X}_t ,*

$$Ds_t(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} r_k(x, t) Ds_{t,k}(x) + \text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)), \quad (30)$$

where

$$\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}) = \sum_k r_k(s_{t,k} - s_t)(s_{t,k} - s_t)^\top. \quad (31)$$

Remark 7 (Diffusion-side analogue of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$). The posterior covariance term $\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x))$ is the diffusion-side analogue of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$: it is the extra curvature induced by uncertainty over branch identity. The corollaries and proposition below characterize its structure: low rank, a Gaussian closed form, an exact posterior-Fisher *matrix* identity, and the probability-flow ODE bridge. Each follows from the mixture-score identity (Theorem 2) by differentiation.

Corollary 2 (Low-rank switching curvature). (proof in A.4) Let $\mathcal{K}_{\text{supp}}(x, t) = \{k : r_k(x, t) > 0\}$ be the posterior support, of size $|\mathcal{K}_{\text{supp}}(x, t)|$. Then

$$\text{rank}(\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x))) \leq \min(d, |\mathcal{K}_{\text{supp}}(x, t)| - 1). \quad (32)$$

In particular, for a binary mixture the responsibility-switching covariance is rank at most one, with single nonzero eigenvalue $r_+(x, t) r_-(x, t) \|s_{t,+}(x) - s_{t,-}(x)\|^2$ along the eigendirection $s_{t,+}(x) - s_{t,-}(x)$.

Corollary 3 (Gaussian-mixture closed form). Suppose each component is Gaussian with common covariance, $p_{t,k}(x) = \mathcal{N}(x; \mu_{t,k}, \Sigma_t)$. Then

$$\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)) = \Sigma_t^{-1} \text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(\mu_{t,K}) \Sigma_t^{-1}, \quad (33)$$

where $\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(\mu_{t,K}) = \sum_k r_k(x, t) (\mu_{t,k} - \bar{\mu}_t)(\mu_{t,k} - \bar{\mu}_t)^\top$ and $\bar{\mu}_t = \sum_k r_k(x, t) \mu_{t,k}$. If additionally $\Sigma_t = \tau_t^2 I$ and $K \in \{+, -\}$ is binary,

$$\text{Tr Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)) = \frac{r_+(x, t) r_-(x, t)}{\tau_t^4} \|\mu_{t,+} - \mu_{t,-}\|^2. \quad (34)$$

Proof. For shared-covariance Gaussians, $s_{t,k}(x) = -\Sigma_t^{-1}(x - \mu_{t,k}) = -\Sigma_t^{-1}x + \Sigma_t^{-1}\mu_{t,k}$. The x -dependent term is K -independent and cancels under centering: $s_{t,k}(x) - s_t(x) = \Sigma_t^{-1}(\mu_{t,k} - \bar{\mu}_t)$. Substituting into the definition of $\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K})$ and factoring out Σ_t^{-1} on both sides gives the displayed formula. The binary isotropic form uses $\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(\mu_K) = r_+ r_- (\mu_+ - \mu_-)(\mu_+ - \mu_-)^\top$, valid because $\mu_\pm - \bar{\mu} = \pm r_\mp (\mu_+ - \mu_-)$. \square

The corollary turns the abstract covariance term into an explicit product of posterior ambiguity $r_+ r_-$, squared component separation $\|\mu_{t,+} - \mu_{t,-}\|^2$, and the inverse noise scale τ_t^{-4} . It is the closed form underlying the responsibility-switching curvature curve of the diffusion-side commitment-window oracle (its binary specialization is worked out in §6.2). Along the noise schedule, the averaged branch-entropy curve and the averaged switching-curvature curve need not peak at the same t : entropy tracks only the uncertainty of the responsibilities, whereas the curvature also carries the schedule factor $\|\mu_{t,+} - \mu_{t,-}\|^2 / \tau_t^4$. A single critical-SNR point is therefore not generic.

The shared-covariance Gaussian-mixture score structure $s_{t,k}(x) - s_t(x) = \Sigma_t^{-1}(\mu_{t,k} - \bar{\mu}_t)$ used in the proof is the central object of Wang and Vastola [51], from which Corollary 3 reads off the responsibility-switching matrix form. The resulting matrix is the shared-covariance GMM instance of the matrix-Tweedie / denoiser-Jacobian identity for the clean-data posterior covariance, $\text{Cov}(X_0 | X_t) = \sigma_t^2 I + \sigma_t^4 \nabla s_t$, established by Manor and Michaeli [35]; the within/between split of that matrix corresponds to the branch decomposition of Theorem 4.

Corollary 4 (Posterior-Fisher identity). (proof in A.5) Adopt Assumption 2 and fix $t \in [0, 1]$. Let $\mathcal{X}_t := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : p_t(x) > 0\}$. For every $x \in \mathcal{X}_t$, the responsibility-switching covariance equals the Fisher information matrix of the categorical branch-posterior map $r(\cdot, t)$ in the variable x :

$$\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)) = \mathcal{I}_x(r(\cdot, t)) := \sum_{k:r_k(x,t)>0} \frac{\nabla_x r_k(x, t) \nabla_x r_k(x, t)^\top}{r_k(x, t)}, \quad (35)$$

where the sum is over indices with $r_k(x, t) > 0$. Under Assumption 2 every $r_k > 0$ on \mathcal{X}_t , so the convention $\nabla_x r_k \nabla_x r_k^\top / r_k := 0$ at $r_k = 0$ is not needed here; it applies only if the assumption is weakened to allow disjoint supports. Taking the trace,

$$\text{Tr Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)) = \sum_{k:r_k(x,t)>0} \frac{\|\nabla_x r_k(x, t)\|^2}{r_k(x, t)}. \quad (36)$$

If additionally $r_k(x, t) > 0$ for all k (the open-simplex regime, so that $\log r_K$ is finite), then

$$\|\nabla_x H(K | X_t = x)\|^2 \leq \text{Tr Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)) \cdot \text{Var}_{K|x,t}(\log r_K). \quad (37)$$

Here $H(K | X_t = x)$ is the pointwise conditional entropy at state x ; its average over Y_t is the branch-entropy diagnostic $H_K(t)$ of Definition 2.

The identity gives a sharper reading of the diffusion-side commitment-window picture than entropy alone: responsibility-switching curvature is large precisely when branch responsibilities change rapidly in x , not merely when their values are uncertain. The entropy-gradient inequality formalizes the same intuition in the opposite direction: branch entropy can vary rapidly in space *only* when the responsibility-switching Fisher term is large.

Remark 8 (Fisher-Rao pullback metric). The matrix of Corollary 4 is the pullback of the simplex Fisher-Rao metric ($g_{\text{FR}}(\dot{r}, \dot{r}) = \sum_k \dot{r}_k^2 / r_k$) under the branch-posterior map $x \mapsto r(\cdot, t)$, that is, $v^\top \text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}) v = \sum_k \langle \nabla_x r_k, v \rangle^2 / r_k$. Categorical / discrete-data flow matching uses the same Fisher-Rao geometry as a transport metric on the simplex itself; here it appears instead as the geometry of branch responsibilities under a state-space flow, which connects to the cosine-schedule optimality of Zhang and Syed [54] in the one-dimensional masking-schedule case.

Proposition 5 (Probability-flow ODE branch bridge). *Adopt Assumption 2, so that s_t and the branch-conditioned scores $s_{t,k}$ exist on $\{p_t > 0\}$. Consider a diffusion probability path generated by an SDE with drift $f_t(x)$ and positive scalar diffusion coefficient $g(t)$, under the regularity conditions of Song et al. [46] §3 (locally Lipschitz f_t on $\{p_t > 0\}$, C^1 diffusion coefficient $g(t) > 0$, sufficient integrability of p_t for the Fokker-Planck equation to hold in the distributional sense, and $s_t \in L^2(p_t)$). The probability-flow ODE has marginal velocity $v_t(x) = f_t(x) - \frac{1}{2} g(t)^2 s_t(x)$. Assume in addition that each branch marginal $p_{t,k}$ solves the Fokker-Planck equation of this same forward SDE (f_t, g) with the t -independent weights π_k of Assumption 2, equivalently that the forward noising acts independently of K ; then the branch-conditioned probability-flow velocities $v_{t,k}(x) = f_t(x) - \frac{1}{2} g(t)^2 s_{t,k}(x)$ are the probability-flow velocities of the branch- k paths, and*

$$v_t(x) = \sum_k r_k(x, t) v_{t,k}(x), \quad (38)$$

and

$$\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(v_{t,K}(x)) = \frac{1}{4} g(t)^4 \text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}(x)). \quad (39)$$

Averaging the trace over $X_t \sim p_t$ gives the diffusion-side between-branch velocity-ambiguity quantity

$$\mathbb{E}_{p_t} \text{Tr Cov}_{K|X_t,t}(v_{t,K}(X_t)) = \frac{1}{4} g(t)^4 \mathbb{E}_{p_t} \text{Tr Cov}_{K|X_t,t}(s_{t,K}(X_t)). \quad (40)$$

Proof. Mixture velocity identity: $\sum_k r_k v_{t,k} = f_t - \frac{1}{2} g(t)^2 \sum_k r_k s_{t,k} = f_t - \frac{1}{2} g(t)^2 s_t = v_t$, using Theorem 2. The drift $f_t(x)$ is K -independent at fixed x and drops out under centering: $v_{t,k}(x) - v_t(x) = -\frac{1}{2} g(t)^2 (s_{t,k}(x) - s_t(x))$. The covariance scaling follows by factoring out the scalar. \square

Remark 9 (Scope of the bridge). The identity relates the diffusion-side score covariance to the between-branch velocity covariance of the same path’s probability-flow ODE through the schedule factor $\frac{1}{4}g(t)^4$. It does *not* extend to arbitrary FM couplings, whose velocity target U_t is set by the source-target coupling and interpolant rather than by the score: the FM-side $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{FM}}(t)$ and the diffusion-side score covariance coincide only for the FM construction whose conditional flow matches the per-branch probability-flow ODE.

Remark 10 (Lineage). Theorem 4 decomposes the marginal score Jacobian over a discrete branch variable K , the diffusion-side counterpart of the velocity decomposition. It connects to a line of diffusion-side posterior-covariance identities: the Tweedie form for the clean-data posterior $X_0 | X_t$ [9], the observed-information identity of Louis [33] (which Corollary 4 instantiates for a path-indexed branch posterior), and the binary score-interface identity of Sarkar [41], recovered as the $|\mathcal{K}| = 2$ case. Unlike the free-entropy speciation criteria of Achilli et al. [1] and the information-thermodynamic accounts of Stančević and Ambrogioni [47], it is a pointwise matrix identity read as a diagnostic rather than a phase-transition or entropy-production statement.

6.2 Binary Gaussian mixture: an explicit instance

We close the score side with the simplest mixture, where the responsibility-switching curvature of Theorem 4 is fully explicit. Consider a symmetric two-component mixture in \mathbb{R}^d :

$$K \in \{-1, +1\}, \quad X_t | K = k \sim \mathcal{N}(km, \tau_t^2 I), \quad (41)$$

with equal priors. We adopt a variance-exploding (VE) convention with $\alpha_t \equiv 1$ throughout this section; the variance-preserving (VP) case follows by rescaling $x \rightarrow x/\alpha_t$. Under this convention, τ_t^2 is the component variance plus diffusion noise variance after scaling.

Proposition 6 (Responsibilities and score). *For the binary Gaussian mixture,*

$$r_+(x, t) = \sigma \left(\frac{2m^\top x}{\tau_t^2} \right), \quad (42)$$

where $\sigma(a) = (1 + e^{-a})^{-1}$. The marginal score is

$$s_t(x) = \frac{m \tanh(m^\top x / \tau_t^2) - x}{\tau_t^2}. \quad (43)$$

Proof. The log-likelihood ratio is

$$\log \frac{p_{t,+}(x)}{p_{t,-}(x)} = -\frac{\|x - m\|^2 - \|x + m\|^2}{2\tau_t^2} = \frac{2m^\top x}{\tau_t^2}. \quad (44)$$

The component scores are $s_{t,k}(x) = (km - x)/\tau_t^2$. Averaging them with $\mathbb{E}[K | x] = \tanh(m^\top x / \tau_t^2)$ yields the score. \square

Proposition 7 (Jacobian and switching curvature). *For the binary Gaussian mixture,*

$$Ds_t(x) = -\frac{1}{\tau_t^2} I + \frac{\text{sech}^2(m^\top x / \tau_t^2)}{\tau_t^4} mm^\top. \quad (45)$$

The responsibility-switching curvature is maximized on the decision boundary $m^\top x = 0$.

Proof. Differentiate $s_t(x) = \tau_t^{-2}m \tanh(a) - \tau_t^{-2}x$ with $a = m^\top x / \tau_t^2$. □

In the simplest mixture the extra curvature is therefore explicit and concentrated near the class boundary. Branch entropy and switching curvature need not peak at the same SNR; they are different diagnostics of a finite commitment window.

7 Couplings and Velocity Ambiguity

Flow Matching exposes a design variable that diffusion usually hides: the *coupling* $\pi(Z, X)$, the rule that pairs each source Z with a target X during training. The same marginals can yield different intermediate distributions and different ambiguity. Each of our six couplings is one such pairing rule. The target X belongs to one *branch* of the data, a mixture mode or class (the branch variable K of §4), written $K_X \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|\}$. The source Z is noise with no branch of its own, so to steer it we attach an external *condition* $C \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|\}$, the branch we want it to flow to. The source therefore carries C rather than a branch label of its own, and a condition-respecting coupling routes each source to a target whose branch matches its condition, $K_X=C$. A rule’s cost then draws on the squared distance $\|Z - X\|^2$ and the two labels K_X and C , and the six rules differ in which of these they read.

	coupling	pairing rule
C_0	independent	pair each source with a uniformly random target ($\pi = p_0 \otimes p_1$).
C_1	Euclidean OT	pair to minimize the total squared distance $\sum \ Z - X\ ^2$.
C_2	condition-aware random	pair each source with a uniformly random target in its own condition branch ($K_X=C$): right branch, random geometry.
$C_3@λ$	semantic-cost OT	pair to minimize $\sum (\ Z - X\ ^2 + λ \mathbf{1}[C \neq K_X])$, the distance plus a penalty $λ$ for each pair that crosses branches.
C_3^∞	blocked OT	the $λ \rightarrow \infty$ limit: Euclidean OT run separately within each $K_X=C$ branch, so a pair never crosses branches.
C_4	geometry-only OT	minimize $\sum \ Z - X\ ^2$ over the nuisance coordinates only, dropping the fixed semantic coordinate from the cost.

Only C_2 , $C_3@λ$, and C_3^∞ read the condition C , so only they can drive the paired branch toward C ; C_0 , C_1 , and C_4 never see C and leave the branch mismatch at chance (Proposition 9). C_1 and C_4 are the same minimize-distance rule on different coordinates: C_1 keeps the branch-carrying coordinate in its cost, so it tends to pair sources and targets that already agree there, while C_4 drops that coordinate and loses the alignment; their gap isolates how much that one coordinate matters. The penalty $λ$ sweeps $C_3@λ$ from C_1 at $λ=0$ to C_3^∞ . Every distance-minimizing rule is solved per minibatch by Hungarian assignment, and C_3^∞ with $C=K_X$ is the deterministic analogue of class-conditional minibatch OT-CFM.

The C_3 penalty adds a condition-mismatch term to the minibatch OT cost, algebraically close to the C²OT family; we compare C_3 and its blocked limit C_3^∞ to the conditional-OT, data-dependent, and neural-OT coupling families in §2.

Proposition 8 (Injective coupling removes velocity ambiguity). *Let $X = \mathcal{T}(Z)$ be a deterministic coupling (transport map) on the standard Borel space \mathbb{R}^d (cf. §3). For fixed t , define $F_t(z) = (1-t)z + t\mathcal{T}(z)$ and $U = \mathcal{T}(Z) - Z$. Assume \mathcal{T} and F_t are Borel measurable, and that F_t is injective on a Borel set $B \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ of full p_0 -measure. Then U is a deterministic function of $Y_t = F_t(Z)$ and*

$$\text{Cov}(U \mid Y_t) = 0 \quad P_{Y_t}\text{-a.s.} \quad (46)$$

Proof. By the Lusin-Souslin theorem (the Borel image of an injective Borel map between standard Borel spaces is Borel, with Borel-measurable inverse), F_t^{-1} is Borel-measurable on $F_t(B)$. Thus $Z = F_t^{-1}(Y_t)$ holds p_0 -almost surely, and $U = \mathcal{T}(F_t^{-1}(Y_t)) - F_t^{-1}(Y_t)$ is $\sigma(Y_t)$ -measurable, so its conditional covariance vanishes P_{Y_t} -a.s. \square

The proposition below states, at the population level, why a condition-blind coupling cannot recover an external condition; it is tested in a later controlled experiment (§9.2). Its companion for label-correct random within-condition couplings (Proposition 11) is stated alongside that experimental setup in §9.2. Both are short consequences of independence and the bivariate Gaussian conditional-variance identity, respectively.

Proposition 9 (Condition-blind couplings cannot recover the condition). *Let $C \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|\}$ be a balanced source condition with $\mathbb{P}(C = k) = 1/|\mathcal{K}|$. Let π be a coupling rule whose paired target index J and the target-bank label vector $(K_{X,j})_j$ are both measurable with respect to a σ -algebra \mathcal{G} satisfying $C \perp \mathcal{G}$ (a condition-blind coupling); examples include minibatch OT on a cost matrix that does not read C , possibly with independent permutation or Sinkhorn randomization. Write K_X^π for the branch label of the target paired with a source sample carrying condition C . Then*

$$K_X^\pi \perp C, \quad \mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi \neq C) = 1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|}. \quad (47)$$

For balanced binary C this equals 1/2 exactly. Only balance of C is needed: $\mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi = C) = \sum_k \mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi = k) \mathbb{P}(C = k) = (1/|\mathcal{K}|) \sum_k \mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi = k) = 1/|\mathcal{K}|$ for any marginal of K_X^π .

Proof. Since $J \in \mathcal{G}$ and the target bank (including each candidate $K_{X,j}$) is part of the data the coupling operates on, $K_X^\pi = K_{X,J}$ is \mathcal{G} -measurable. By hypothesis $C \perp \mathcal{G}$, hence $C \perp K_X^\pi$. Using $\mathbb{P}(C = k) = 1/|\mathcal{K}|$,

$$\mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi = C) = \sum_k \mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi = k) \mathbb{P}(C = k) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|}. \quad \square$$

Remark 11 (Edge cases). The proposition is stated at the *population* level: \mathcal{G} encodes the entire coupling computation, including the full minibatch of source and target vectors $(Z_1, \dots, Z_n, X_1, \dots, X_n)$ but not the source condition vector (C_1, \dots, C_n) . Stochastic coupling rules (randomized Hungarian, Sinkhorn) are covered by absorbing the auxiliary randomization W into \mathcal{G} as long as $W \perp C$; class-conditional minibatch samplers, which condition batch construction on C , violate the hypothesis and are not covered. The proposition therefore predicts that the independent, Euclidean-OT, and geometry-only-OT couplings all leave the mismatch rate at the random baseline regardless of geometric efficiency, because none of their cost matrices reads the source condition C .

The probability value generalizes beyond the balanced case. For general marginals p of C and q of K_X^π , $\mathbb{P}(K_X^\pi = C) = \langle p, q \rangle$, which only balance of C collapses to $1/|\mathcal{K}|$ independently of q . If C and K_X^π have joint dependence in the data law, condition-blindness still forces (C, K_X^π) to factor as the

Algorithm 1 Branch-variance decomposition (k NN estimator at a fixed time t). The biased $1/k$ scatter convention makes the returned $\widehat{\mathcal{A}}_v, \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}}, \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}}$ exactly additive; integrating over the t -grid gives the reported curves. The step-by-step measurement procedure is in Appendix I.

Require: samples $\{(Z_i, X_i, K_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, time t , neighbor count k

Ensure: $\widehat{\mathcal{A}}_v(t), \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}}(t), \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}}(t)$ with $\widehat{\mathcal{A}}_v = \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}} + \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}}$

```

1: for  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
2:    $Y_i \leftarrow (1-t)Z_i + tX_i, \quad U_i \leftarrow X_i - Z_i$  ▷ interpolant state and velocity
3: end for
4: build a  $k$ NN index on  $\{Y_i\}$  in  $Y_t$ -space;  $S_v, S_w, S_b \leftarrow 0$ 
5: for each query  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
6:    $\mathcal{J}_i \leftarrow$  the  $k$  nearest neighbors of  $Y_i$ ;  $\bar{u} \leftarrow \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} U_j$  ▷ neighborhood, local mean
7:    $S_v \leftarrow S_v + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \|U_j - \bar{u}\|^2$  ▷ total local scatter
8:   for each branch  $b$  present in  $\mathcal{J}_i$  do
9:      $m_b \leftarrow \text{mean}\{U_j : j \in \mathcal{J}_i, K_j = b\}$  ▷ per-branch local mean
10:     $S_w \leftarrow S_w + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i, K_j = b} \|U_j - m_b\|^2$  ▷ within-branch scatter
11:   end for
12:    $S_b \leftarrow S_b + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \|m_{K_j} - \bar{u}\|^2$  ▷ between-branch scatter
13: end for
14: return  $\widehat{\mathcal{A}}_v \leftarrow S_v/N, \quad \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}} \leftarrow S_w/N, \quad \widehat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}} \leftarrow S_b/N$ 

```

product of marginals, so the matched pair carries no more $C-K_X$ dependence than the unpaired target bank already has.

Condition-blindness rules out recovering an *external* label, but it does not prevent a Euclidean coupling from aligning a weak semantic *coordinate* carried in the geometry, and that alignment is what lowers the semantic ambiguity. The following population statement is distribution-free in the semantic marginal, so we state it here with the general coupling theory; its quantitative within/between consequence under the bivariate-Gaussian construction is given alongside the data it explains (Proposition 12, §9.2).

Proposition 10 (Euclidean OT aligns the semantic coordinate). (proof in A.6) *Suppose the source $Z = [Z_G, Z_S]$ and target $X = [X_G, X_S]$ split into a geometry block and a one-dimensional semantic coordinate that are independent in both marginals, and the squared cost separates as $\|Z - X\|^2 = \|Z_G - X_G\|^2 + (Z_S - X_S)^2$. Write $\rho_S := \text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S)$ under the resulting coupling. Then Euclidean OT (C_1) factorizes into the geometry-block and semantic-block optimal couplings, and its semantic factor is the monotone rearrangement of Z_S and X_S ; hence $\rho_S(C_1) > 0$ whenever X_S is non-degenerate, even though C_1 is condition-blind in the sense of Proposition 9. The geometry-only coupling (C_4), whose cost drops the semantic coordinate, pairs the semantic values independently, so $\rho_S(C_4) = 0$.*

8 Oracle and Proxy Diagnostic Recipe

Before reporting experiments, we collect the diagnostic variables introduced in the preceding sections into a single recipe for computing BVD on a representative oracle or a held-out training subset, when explicit labels, conditions, or faithful proxy branch estimators are available. The recipe restates each symbol so it can be followed without re-reading the preceding theorems.

Oracle versus proxy branch variables. The recipe *identifies the oracle within/between split* when K is an oracle branch label or an explicit conditioning input (the additive identity $\mathcal{A}_v = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}} + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ itself holds population-level by total covariance regardless of the partition). When K is estimated from a representation or classifier (e.g., k -means on a learned embedding, a downstream classifier head, or a VAE / CLIP cluster), the resulting $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, and R_{switch} become *proxy diagnostics* relative to that estimator, only as faithful as it is. The bound direction is fixed only when the proxy is a coarsening of the oracle branch variable: then $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$ over-estimates the oracle within-branch value while $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ and R_{switch} under-estimate theirs (Proposition 2). For a non-nested proxy such as k -means or a downstream classifier the direction is not guaranteed (Appendix I, step 5), so we report the estimator used and, when available, its validation accuracy alongside the diagnostic curves. At scale on natural images or language, the recipe takes a domain-appropriate branch estimator as its input.

Diagnostic family. Six quantities together describe the ambiguity structure of a generative probability path with discrete (or discretizable) branch variable K and optional external condition C :

- $\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr Cov}(U \mid Y_t, T=t)$: the conditional velocity variance, i.e., the irreducible L^2 regression floor of any single-valued velocity field at time t .
- $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr } \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(U \mid Y_t, K, T=t) \mid Y_t, T=t]$: the part of $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ that survives even after conditioning on the branch identity K ; it captures within-branch local uncertainty.
- $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) = \mathbb{E}_Y \text{Tr Cov}(\mathbb{E}[U \mid Y_t, K, T=t] \mid Y_t, T=t)$: the complement; it captures the part of $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ that comes from incompatible-direction averaging across branches.
- $R_{\text{switch}}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) / (\mathcal{A}_v(t) + \epsilon_0)$, with ϵ_0 a small numerical stabilizer (Definition 2): the fraction of $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ that is between-branch. High $R_{\text{switch}}(t)$ indicates a switching-dominated regime.
- $H_K(t)$: the branch-entropy diagnostic for diffusion-side analyses; tracks how concentrated the branch posterior $r_k(x, t)$ is at noise level t .
- $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t \mid C)$: the semantic-coordinate-only conditional ambiguity normalized by $\mathbb{E}\|U_S\|^2 + \epsilon_0$ (Definition 2); used when an external condition C is available and we restrict attention to a semantic subspace S .

Branch-variance decomposition (BVD), $\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$, holds exactly (law of total covariance); the score-side analogue is the mixture-score Jacobian decomposition into within-branch curvature plus posterior-covariance of component scores. From samples these three terms are estimated by the local k NN scatter of Algorithm 1; the step-by-step measurement procedure (choosing the branch variable, the t -grid, the proxy bound direction, and the coupling comparison) is given in Appendix I.

Reading the curves. A practitioner running the diagnostic (Algorithm 1) should look for three signals. First, the *commitment window*: the interval of t (or log SNR on the diffusion side) where $H_K(t)$ drops from $\log |\mathcal{K}|$ to near zero while $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ remains non-trivial. Inside this window the regression target is structurally averaged; outside it the target is approximately deterministic.

Second, the *within-vs-between balance*, read off $R_{\text{switch}}(t)$: a high value indicates the irreducible floor is dominated by incompatible-destination averaging across branches; a low value indicates the floor is mostly within-branch local noise that no coupling intervention can remove. Third, the *coupling sensitivity*: sweep the coupling and watch whether $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ or $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t | C)$ drops; a drop concentrated in $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ while $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$ stays put confirms that the intervention is targeting the right failure mode.

9 Experiments

Our four main experiments increase in realism, and the last two are on real data. **E2** (§9.1) verifies on a crossing-path oracle that the velocity floor $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ matches its closed form, so the decomposed quantity is exact. **E3** (§9.2), a 33-dimensional controlled experiment in which geometry and semantic identity are deliberately decoupled, is our primary mechanism experiment: it establishes that the decomposition responds to the source-target coupling and that a condition-blind coupling cannot recover an external condition. These two are synthetic because only a controlled construction supplies closed-form ground truth and a tunable geometry-semantics decoupling. The remaining two are on *real data*: **E5** (§9.3) audits CIFAR-10 CLIP features and shows a label-free proxy recovers the oracle between-branch signal across splits from binary to ten-way once the neighborhood bandwidth tracks the branch count, and **E7** (§9.4) shows on a trained CIFAR Flow-Matching model that the between-branch ambiguity $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ predicts, in both profile and magnitude, the velocity-MSE recovered by branch conditioning (Proposition 1). The synthetic results (E2, E3) establish the mechanism that the real-data results (E5, E7) then exploit.

Unless noted otherwise, ambiguity is estimated with the default k NN covariance estimator and switching-ratio stabilizer of the recipe in §8, with bandwidth sensitivity reported in Appendix I. Conditional metrics in E3 are estimated by building separate k NN graphs within each value of the external condition C , which matches a conditional velocity model $v_\theta(Y_t, t, C)$. Reported \pm values in tables and figures are sample standard deviations over seeds, not confidence intervals, with per-experiment seed counts in §9.6.

9.1 Flow-Matching crossing-path oracle (E2)

Setup. We use two probabilistic branches in \mathbb{R}^2 . Branch A transports from $(-1, 0)$ to $(1, 0)$, and branch B transports from $(0, -1)$ to $(0, 1)$, each with isotropic endpoint noise $\sigma_b = 0.1$. The two line paths cross near the origin at $t = 1/2$. The point evaluation $t = 1/2$ below should be read as Proposition 4 specialized to a spatial neighborhood shrinking to the crossing point $y = 0$ at $t = 1/2$, made meaningful by the finite endpoint noise $\sigma_b > 0$.

At the crossing time $t = 1/2$, the posterior branch probability is $1/2$. For a d -dimensional isotropic branch, the within-branch term is

$$\text{Tr Cov}(U | Y_t, K) = \frac{d\sigma_b^2}{(1-t)^2 + t^2}. \quad (48)$$

This follows from the Schur-complement reduction

$$\text{Cov}(U | Y, K) = \text{Cov}(U | K) - \text{Cov}(U, Y | K) \text{Cov}(Y | K)^{-1} \text{Cov}(Y, U | K),$$

Figure 3: Flow-Matching crossing-path oracle (E2). At the geometric crossing, conditional velocity directions are incompatible, so the single-valued FM target becomes their posterior average and the irreducible error is dominated by between-branch ambiguity. Panels: (a) sampled states at the branch endpoints and the $t = 1/2$ crossing; (b) within/between decomposition of the velocity-variance floor, overlaying closed-form curves with empirical k NN estimates; (c) normalized ambiguity, the explained-variance complement $1 - R_v^2$, branch entropy H , and the switching ratio R_{switch} (empirical and closed-form); (d) bandwidth sensitivity of the estimate at $t = 1/2$.

using $\text{Cov}(U | K) = 2\sigma_b^2 I$, $\text{Cov}(U, Y | K) = (2t-1)\sigma_b^2 I$, and the identity $2((1-t)^2 + t^2) - (2t-1)^2 = 1$. Specializing to $d = 2$, $t = 1/2$, and $\|u_A - u_B\|^2 = 8$, we obtain

$$\mathcal{A}_v(1/2) = \frac{2\sigma_b^2}{(1/2)^2 + (1/2)^2} + \frac{1}{4}\|u_A - u_B\|^2 = 0.04 + 2 = 2.04. \quad (49)$$

The between-branch closed form $\frac{1}{4}\|u_A - u_B\|^2$ uses two properties of the E2 setting at the crossing point $y = 0$: branch-deterministic terminal velocities (so $\mathbb{E}[U|Y, K] = u_K$ is y -independent in the $\sigma_b \rightarrow 0$ idealization), and posterior balance $r_A(0) = 1/2$. It is therefore the specialization of general BVD to the crossing point at $t = 1/2$; finite endpoint noise σ_b adds an $O(\sigma_b^2)$ correction that the Monte-Carlo estimate captures.

Coupling	mismatch	T_{full}	T_{geom}	T_{sem}	$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2} C)$	$H(K_X Y_{1/2}, C)/\log 2$
C_0 independent	0.501 ± 0.005	66.234 ± 0.075	63.970 ± 0.078	2.264 ± 0.021	0.985 ± 0.013	0.977 ± 0.001
C_1 Euclidean OT	0.500 ± 0.003	32.746 ± 0.038	31.699 ± 0.039	1.048 ± 0.009	0.845 ± 0.007	0.967 ± 0.001
C_2 cond.-aware random	0.000 ± 0.000	66.202 ± 0.094	63.954 ± 0.099	2.249 ± 0.030	0.879 ± 0.013	0.000 ± 0.000
$C_3@\lambda=1$	0.420 ± 0.003	32.770 ± 0.040	31.716 ± 0.040	1.054 ± 0.012	0.840 ± 0.009	0.936 ± 0.004
$C_3@\lambda=3$	0.277 ± 0.003	33.065 ± 0.038	31.991 ± 0.040	1.074 ± 0.010	0.821 ± 0.005	0.734 ± 0.008
$C_3@\lambda=10$	0.042 ± 0.002	34.374 ± 0.037	33.140 ± 0.037	1.234 ± 0.018	0.728 ± 0.012	0.106 ± 0.009
$C_3@\lambda=30$	0.018 ± 0.002	34.639 ± 0.067	33.372 ± 0.064	1.267 ± 0.022	0.713 ± 0.010	0.048 ± 0.009
$C_3@\lambda=100$	0.019 ± 0.003	34.641 ± 0.050	33.377 ± 0.044	1.264 ± 0.015	0.708 ± 0.008	0.051 ± 0.010
C_3^∞ blocked OT	0.000 ± 0.000	34.861 ± 0.022	33.563 ± 0.029	1.298 ± 0.017	0.694 ± 0.008	0.000 ± 0.000
C_4 geometry-only OT	0.498 ± 0.004	33.448 ± 0.037	31.181 ± 0.044	2.267 ± 0.024	0.983 ± 0.011	0.983 ± 0.000

Table 1: Primary coupling-mechanism experiment (E3), results over 10 seeds; the \pm seed variation aggregates source / target / condition resampling, minibatch order, and k NN estimator noise. The mismatch column is $\mathbb{P}(K_X \neq C)$ after coupling. T_{full} , T_{geom} , T_{sem} are raw Euclidean transport costs after assignment with no semantic-mismatch penalty (T_{geom} on the 32-D nuisance coordinates, T_{sem} on the 1-D semantic coordinate; see Appendix I). The right-most columns report the symmetric-midpoint slice $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t=1/2|C)$ and $H(K_X|Y_{1/2}, C)/\log 2$ at the headline $k = 80$; Figure 4 bar plots use \max_t versions. The k , λ , and ε sensitivity sweeps are detailed in the Reproducibility paragraph (§9.6).

Results. Using $N = 120,000$ path samples and a single seed, with the default bandwidth $k = 80$, Figure 3 shows that the biased plug-in k NN estimate at $t = 1/2$ is $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_v(1/2) = 2.0150$. This sits 1.23% below the closed-form value $\mathcal{A}_v(1/2) = 2.0400$, consistent with the $k/(k-1) = 80/79$ finite-sample correction of the biased $1/k$ plug-in convention (Appendix I); applying that correction gives $2.0150 \times 80/79 = 2.0405$, which matches the closed form to within 0.025% relative error. The within/between split is exactly additive ($\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(1/2) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(1/2) = 0.0391 + 1.9758 = 2.0149 = \hat{\mathcal{A}}_v(1/2)$ up to rounding). Both $\mathcal{A}_v(1/2)$ and its exact branch decomposition are thus confirmed against the closed form.

At the crossing, $H_K(1/2)/\log 2 = 1$ and $R_{\text{switch}}(1/2) \approx 0.98$, so almost all of the floor is between-branch ambiguity. A 3-seed bandwidth sweep over $k \in \{10, 30, 50, 80, 100, 200, 400\}$ (Figure 3d), after applying the k -dependent $k/(k-1)$ finite-sample correction at each bandwidth, agrees with the closed-form value to within 0.07% relative error in the 3-seed mean.

Companion floor verifications (E1, E4). Two appendix experiments (Appendix B) verify the same velocity floor in adjacent settings. E1, a binary Gaussian diffusion oracle, traces a finite middle-SNR commitment window and matches the closed-form responsibility-switching curvature. E4 trains small fixed- t MLPs and finds the held-out loss saturates the oracle floor $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$, with the residual approximation error two to three orders of magnitude below it.

9.2 Primary coupling-mechanism experiment in nuisance-dominated space (E3)

E2 confirmed that $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ is the exact floor; we now vary the source-target coupling to test whether the within/between split responds as the theory predicts, in a setting where geometry and semantics are decoupled by construction.

Figure 4: Primary coupling-mechanism experiment (E3), main results summary: (a) mismatch rate by coupling, (b) max- t semantic-only conditional ambiguity, (c) max- t conditional branch entropy, (d) Pareto trade-off (T_{full} vs max- t semantic ambiguity). Read with the Results text below.

Setup. We construct a 33-dimensional controlled conditional-mismatch experiment. The source is $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_{33})$ with an external condition $C \in \{-1, +1\}$ independent of Z . The target is $X = [G, S]$, where $G \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_{32})$ is nuisance geometry and $S = aK_X + \sigma_s \varepsilon$ is a weak semantic coordinate with $a = 0.5$ and $\sigma_s = 1.0$. This is the binary instance of the branch set \mathcal{K} ($|\mathcal{K}| = 2$), with the two branches encoded as $K_X, C \in \{-1, +1\}$ in place of $\{1, 2\}$ so the linear coordinate S is symmetric about zero. Thus semantic information occupies one weak dimension and is dominated by 32 nuisance dimensions. We compare independent coupling (C_0), Euclidean OT (C_1), condition-aware random pairing (C_2), semantic-cost OT (C_3) swept over $\lambda \in \{1, 3, 10, 30, 100\}$ together with the hard-blocked limit C_3^∞ , and geometry-only OT on G (C_4). Conditional metrics are computed by building separate k NN graphs within each condition C . All OT couplings are computed by minibatch Hungarian assignment with $N=20,000$ source-target pairs per seed, batch size 1024, 10 seeds, and an independent random permutation before each minibatch is formed; the C_3 semantic penalty is used only to compute the assignment, and all transport costs reported below are raw Euclidean

costs after assignment. Reported numbers use $k=80$ for the k NN ambiguity estimator; bandwidth sensitivity over $k \in \{30, 80, 200\}$ is summarized in Appendix I.

Results. Table 1 and Figure 4 show that on *external-condition mismatch*, C_1 and C_4 are indistinguishable: both have mismatch rate about 0.50 and near-maximal conditional entropy, as required by Proposition 9 for any condition-blind coupling on a balanced source condition. On *coordinate-level semantic ambiguity*, however, C_1 is strictly lower in semantic ambiguity than C_4 : $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2} | C)$ is 0.845 for C_1 vs 0.983 for C_4 , a gap of 0.14 (Table 1, midpoint slice; the Figure 4 bars report the \max_t version). The mechanism is the semantic endpoint correlation $\rho_S := \text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S)$: C_1 's Euclidean cost includes the semantic coordinate, inducing $\rho_S > 0$ even though C_1 cannot recover the external condition, while C_4 ignores the semantic coordinate so $\rho_S \approx 0$ (Proposition 10). A given ρ_S leaves the semantic ambiguity in closed form (Proposition 12), strictly decreasing in $|\rho_S|$, which is why C_1 undercuts C_4 . The E3c scaling sweep (§B.1) measures this effect across the geometry dimension D_G and semantic gap a , where the measured ρ_S tracks the direction of the C_1 -vs- C_4 gap.

Semantic-cost OT traces a smooth Pareto frontier: at $\lambda = 10$, mismatch drops to 0.042 ± 0.002 while raw Euclidean full-state transport increases from 32.746 to 34.374, about a 5.0% overhead, and the geometric component alone increases from 31.70 to 33.14 ($\sim 4.5\%$); at $\lambda = 30$, mismatch drops further to 0.018 ± 0.002 . C_2 achieves perfect label matching yet retains high semantic-only ambiguity, because random within-condition pairing creates long paths, so semantic consistency without geometric efficiency leaves the floor high. Per- t conditional profiles for all 10 couplings are in Figure 5.

The empirical content of the C_3 family at finite λ is the shape of this Pareto, not the trivial $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ limit: the C_3 cost matrix adds $\lambda \cdot \mathbf{1}[C \neq K_X]$ to the geometric cost, so by construction $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ forces within-condition matching and drives mismatch to zero. The non-trivial diagnostic finding at this configuration is the *magnitude* of the geometric overhead required at the finite λ values where mismatch already saturates: here only $\sim 5\%$ at $\lambda = 10$ buys a $12\times$ mismatch reduction against the theorem-bounded 0.50 baseline.

The hard-blocked baseline C_3^∞ solves Hungarian OT separately within each $C=K_X$ block. A paired-seed comparison (the 10 seeds reseed source / target / condition identically, so the difference cancels the shared resampling noise) shows the C_3 family approaching it smoothly: mismatch saturates by $\lambda = 30$ (0.018, statistically indistinguishable from $\lambda = 100$ at $n = 10$), while the transport cost and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S$ keep closing toward the blocked endpoint through $\lambda = 100$, where they sit within $\sim 0.6\%$ and a few hundredths of C_3^∞ respectively. The paired differences are small but resolvable, well below the cross-coupling seed spread in Table 1.

Appendix J additionally reports an entropy-regularized Sinkhorn variant of these couplings: Sinkhorn preserves the qualitative ordering at every $\varepsilon \in \{0.03, 0.1, 0.3\}$, with small ε approximating the Hungarian limit and large ε partially washing out the semantic-cost signal.

Two features of Table 1 admit a closed-form explanation: (i) the ≈ 0.50 mismatch rate of C_0 , C_1 , and C_4 matches the population-level conclusion of Proposition 9 to within one binomial standard deviation ($\sqrt{p(1-p)/N} \approx 0.0035$ at $N = 20,000$), since none of these costs reads the source condition C ; and (ii) the 0.879 value of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(1/2 | C)$ for C_2 , despite $\mathbb{P}(K_X = C) = 1$, matches the within-condition floor of Proposition 11 below: at $t = 1/2$ the proposition gives $\text{Var}(U_S | Y_{1/2}, C) = 1 + \sigma_s^2 = 2$, and normalizing by $\mathbb{E}\|U_S\|^2 = 2 + a^2 = 9/4$ predicts $8/9 \approx 0.889$ (measured 0.879, within 1.1%). Predictions 1 and 2 from §9.5 are exactly the qualitative readings of these two propositions. Unlike

Figure 5: Primary coupling-mechanism experiment (E3) conditional t -profiles with 10-seed standard deviation. (a) full-state conditional $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v(t | C)$, (b) semantic-only conditional $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t | C)$, (c) semantic-subspace conditional branch entropy $H(K_X | Y_t^S, C)$, (d) semantic-only switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}^S(t | C)$. The semantic-only panels (b) and (d) reveal effects that are diluted in the full-state panel (a) by high-dimensional nuisance coordinates.

the general condition-blind result (Proposition 9, §7), the proposition below is a special case tied to this experiment’s bivariate-Gaussian construction, so we state it here alongside the data it explains rather than in the theory sections.

Proposition 11 (Label-correct coupling leaves a positive floor). (proof in A.7) *Consider the one-dimensional semantic coordinate of E3. Let $C \in \{-1, +1\}$ and assume that, conditionally on $C = c$, $Z_S \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and $X_S \sim \mathcal{N}(ac, \sigma_s^2)$ are independent (condition-aware random pairing), with $a > 0$ and $\sigma_s > 0$. Let $Y_t^S = (1 - t)Z_S + tX_S$ and $U_S = X_S - Z_S$. Then $\mathbb{P}(K_X = C) = 1$, yet for every $t \in (0, 1)$,*

$$\text{Var}(U_S | Y_t^S, C) = 1 + \sigma_s^2 - \frac{(t\sigma_s^2 - (1 - t))^2}{(1 - t)^2 + t^2\sigma_s^2} > 0. \quad (50)$$

The right-hand side is independent of a , attains its maximum $1 + \sigma_s^2$ at $t_\star = 1/(1 + \sigma_s^2)$, and takes the endpoint values σ_s^2 at $t = 0$ and 1 at $t = 1$.

In the E3 instantiation ($a = 0.5$, $\sigma_s = 1$), the maximum $t_\star = 1/2$ coincides with the symmetric midpoint slice reported in Table 1, and the closed-form value 2 normalizes (using $\mathbb{E}[U_S^2 | C] =$

$1 + \sigma_s^2 + a^2 = 2.25$) to $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(1/2 | C) = 8/9 \approx 0.889$ (empirical 0.879 ± 0.013). The biased $1/k$ plug-in convention (Appendix I) predicts a finite-sample correction of $(k-1)/k = 79/80$ at $k = 80$, giving $8/9 \times 79/80 = 0.8778$ as the expected biased estimate of the closed-form value; this lies within one seed-SD of the empirical 0.879, so the residual gap is accounted for by the same finite-sample correction exposed by the E2 verification (§9.1). A second-order residual is consistent with the fact that C_2 is implemented as a Hungarian-assignment on a random cost matrix within each condition, rather than as a strictly i.i.d. random pairing.

The C_1 -versus- C_4 gap has the same kind of closed form. Proposition 10 fixes the population mechanism, $\rho_S(C_1) > 0$ against $\rho_S(C_4) = 0$. That proposition is a population-OT statement, while E3 realizes the coupling by minibatch Hungarian assignment, so the finite-batch ρ_S inherits the sign that separates C_1 from C_4 while its magnitude depends on the batch size. The next proposition turns a given ρ_S into the semantic ambiguity it leaves, in the bivariate-Gaussian endpoint model.

Proposition 12 (Endpoint correlation sets the semantic ambiguity). (proof in A.8) *Model the semantic endpoints of a coupling as jointly Gaussian with $\mathbb{E}Z_S = \mathbb{E}X_S = 0$, $\text{Var}(Z_S) = 1$, $\text{Var}(X_S) = q$, and $\text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S) = \rho_S$. With $U_S = X_S - Z_S$ and $Y_t^S = (1-t)Z_S + tX_S$, the normalized semantic ambiguity at the symmetric midpoint is*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\tfrac{1}{2}) = 1 - \frac{(q-1)^2}{(q+1)^2 - 4\rho_S^2 q}, \quad (51)$$

which is strictly decreasing in $|\rho_S|$ for $q \neq 1$. Hence a coupling with $\rho_S > 0$ (such as C_1 , by Proposition 10) attains a strictly smaller semantic ambiguity than one with $\rho_S = 0$ (such as C_4).

Proposition 12 models the semantic endpoints marginally over C , so its $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2})$ matches the conditional $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2} | C)$ of Table 1 in direction rather than exact value. Across couplings the target second moment $q = \text{Var}(X_S)$ is fixed by the data, so only ρ_S moves and raising it lowers the floor; the Gaussian model gives the direction and a closed form, while the exact values for the bimodal E3 target $X_S = aK_X + \sigma_s \varepsilon$ are the measured $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2} | C)$ of Table 1 and the ρ_S sweep of E3c (§B.1).

Geometry-aligned controls and reflow (E3a, E3b, E6). Three further appendix experiments probe the coupling mechanism in geometry-aligned settings. E3a and E3b (Appendix B.4) are positive controls in which Euclidean OT removes the ambiguity once geometry encodes the branch; E3b additionally gives a machine-precision check of the branch-refinement identity (Proposition 2). E6 (Appendix C) tests the first-iteration reflow-locality conjecture (§10) on the E3b four-mode target and finds the between-branch reduction concentrated where the initial coupling switches most.

9.3 Real-data branch validation on CIFAR-10 CLIP features (E5)

Controlled experiments verify BVD where the branch variable and coupling are known by construction, which gives closed-form ground truth that real data cannot provide. This subsection asks whether the same decomposition reads genuine branch structure on real data, and whether it can be used without branch labels. Branch labels serve to validate the unsupervised proxy: once an oracle labeling is shown to produce branch signal beyond a cardinality baseline and the proxy is shown to recover that signal, the diagnostic runs from the validated proxy alone. We validate

Figure 6: Real-data branch validation on CIFAR-10 (E5). Shaded bands in panels (b)-(d) are resampling standard deviations across seeds. (a) Model-free CLIP-feature audit ($N = 8000$ per seed, three seeds): de-biased $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ under the oracle labeling (normalized to 1) and under the unsupervised k -means proxy, read as the window-averaged recovery over the ambiguity window ($t \leq 1/2$) at a matched 40 neighbors per branch. The proxy reproduces the oracle between-branch signal across the binary, three-way, and ten-way splits, sitting slightly above the oracle at every split; the bandwidth-versus-cardinality scaling that this requires is detailed in Appendix D.5. (b) Model-grounded real-path audit ($N = 2000$ per seed, five seeds) using one-step endpoint neighborhoods from a trained unconditional CIFAR Flow-Matching model: de-biased $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ under oracle and proxy labelings is large near the noise end and decays through the commitment window, changing sign near $t \approx 1/2$. (c) Per- t proxy recovery is near 0.98 at $t = 0.1$ and declines to about 0.66 by $t = 0.4$, then becomes uninformative once the oracle signal approaches zero. (d) Branch observability (neighborhood class purity) rises with t .

on CIFAR-10 [27] in two settings, a model-free feature audit and an audit grounded in a trained Flow-Matching model, de-biasing every reading against a cardinality null. We use the same biased $1/k$ k NN plug-in estimator and conventions as the diagnostic recipe (§8) and Appendix I, so E5 introduces no new estimator. A further real-feature proxy-quality and stability check on the same embeddings is deferred to Appendix G (E5a), where Figure 19 shows the CLIP and weak-projection proxies against the oracle branch decomposition.

Cardinality-de-biased between-branch signal. $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ grows with the number of branches K even for a random partition, so a raw comparison across labelings confounds semantics with cardinality. For a labeling with K branches, let $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ denote its between-branch ambiguity and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{rand}}$ the same quantity under a balanced random K -way partition of the same anchors (each partition assigns the anchors to K equal-size groups uniformly at random). The cardinality-de-biased signal is

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}} := \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}} - \mathbb{E} \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{rand}},$$

with the expectation estimated from six random partitions per seed. A positive $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}}$ means the labeling concentrates velocity-mean variance beyond what its cardinality alone buys. The label-free deployability is measured by the proxy recovery ratio

$$\text{Recovery} := \frac{\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}}(\text{proxy})}{\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}}(\text{oracle})}.$$

The model-grounded real-path audit reports this ratio per t (per- t recovery); the model-free feature audit reports the window-averaged recovery, the ratio of the two de-biased signals each averaged over the ambiguity window $t \leq 1/2$. This ratio is read only where the de-biased oracle denominator is clearly positive (well above the null); near and after the zero crossing the per-seed ratios straddle zero and become unstable (a ratio of two small noisy quantities), so cells where the recovery is dominated by this ratio noise are not used as evidence and are marked with a dash in the tables.

Model-free feature audit. On CIFAR-10 CLIP ViT-B/32 [39] features (oracle = the dataset class coarsened to K branches, proxy = unsupervised k -means with K clusters), the de-biased oracle between-branch signal is positive in the ambiguity window, and the unsupervised proxy reproduces it at every granularity once the bandwidth tracks the cardinality, matching the oracle at $K=2$ and slightly exceeding it at finer K (Figure 6a). The de-biasing subtracts a cardinality null whose magnitude scales as K/k (a random K -partition of the k neighbors leaves $\sim k/K$ per branch), so resolving more branches requires proportionally more neighbors and k must grow with K . Holding ~ 20 to 40 neighbors per branch and reading the recovery in the ambiguity window ($t \leq 1/2$, where the between-branch signal is present), the proxy recovers 0.997 to 1.011 of the oracle signal at $K = 2$, 1.002 to 1.041 at $K = 3$, and 1.063 to 1.066 at $K = 10$ (3 seeds, $N = 8000$). At a single fixed bandwidth the recovery is artificially depressed at fine K , with the full-grid de-biased signal even falling below the cardinality null at $K = 10$, $k = 80$ ($\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}} = -0.011 \pm 0.001$). This happens because too few neighbors per branch under-resolve the null, and because the committed large- t regime, where no branch signal remains, contributes only ratio noise to a full-grid average; scaling k with K and reading the ambiguity window removes both (Appendix D.5).

Model-grounded real-path audit. We then ground the audit in a trained model: an unconditional CIFAR-10 Flow-Matching model trained with independent (C_0) coupling. For a real image x (oracle = its dataset class), source noise z , and real velocity $U = x - z$, the interpolant is $Y_t = (1-t)z + tx$ and the model’s one-step endpoint estimate is $\hat{X} = Y_t + (1-t)v_\theta(Y_t, t)$. We build the local neighborhood on $\text{CLIP}(\hat{X})$, because the raw pixel state Y_t does not localize the branch while the predicted endpoint does, and decompose the real U over oracle, proxy, and null labelings. The de-biased oracle signal at $K = 2$ is large near the noise end and decays monotonically with t , from $+13.6 \pm 1.9$ at $t = 0.1$ to near zero by $t = 0.5$ and below zero by $t = 0.6$ (Figure 6b). This is the expected ambiguity-to-commitment profile: branches are maximally ambiguous near noise

Figure 7: Real-model branch-conditioning payoff (E7), three seeds, bands are sample SD. (a) velocity-MSE of the unconditional, true-label conditional, and label-averaged conditional fields. (b) the strict payoff: the realized cross-model gain Δ_{cross} and the posterior-weighted between-branch spread S_{post} in the ambiguity window ($t \leq 0.5$ shaded, mean ratio $\Delta_{\text{cross}}/S_{\text{post}} = 1.05$). (c) the CLIP-free same-checkpoint check, Δ_{within} versus the uniform class spread S_{uni} (cosine 0.9988, ratio 1.14). (d) S_{post} predicts Δ_{cross} along the $y = x$ line over $t \leq 0.5$.

and have committed by the data end, after which the two-way oracle no longer captures branch divergence. Neighborhood class purity rises from 0.13 to 0.42 over the same window (Figure 6d), confirming the transition from mixed to committed neighborhoods. The k -means proxy recovers the oracle signal in the ambiguity regime (recovery $0.98 \rightarrow 0.66$ for $t \in [0.1, 0.4]$, Figure 6c) and becomes uninformative once the oracle signal approaches zero. The full protocol, branch coarsenings, and the per- t table are in Appendix D (Table 3). The neighborhood and the proxy are built in CLIP feature space, and the reported \pm values measure the spread under data and noise resampling at a fixed trained model.

9.4 Real-model branch-conditioning payoff (E7)

E5 showed that on real CIFAR-10 a label-free proxy recovers the oracle between-branch signal. We now ask whether that number has decision value for a trained model. Proposition 1 gives a direct payoff: replacing a single shared velocity field by a branch-conditioned field reduces the irreducible velocity-MSE by exactly $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$. We test this identity on existing CIFAR Flow-Matching

checkpoints, in the model’s own velocity space, without additional training.

Setup. We use an unconditional and a class-conditional CIFAR-10 Flow-Matching checkpoint, the same U-Net up to the class embedding, the same independent (C_0) coupling, and the same 50k-step budget (EMA weights). The branch variable K is the full ten-way CIFAR-10 class label. On held-out test pairs with $Y_t = (1 - t)Z + tX$ and $U = X - Z$ ($N = 2000$, three seeds, errors summed over the 3072 velocity dimensions), we measure the unconditional error $\text{MSE}_{\text{uncond}}$, the true-label conditional error $\text{MSE}_{\text{cond,true}}$ (the MSE_{cond} of Remark 3), and the label-averaged conditional error $\text{MSE}_{\text{cond,avg}}$ (the conditional velocity averaged over all class labels at a fixed Y_t , then scored against U ; Figure 7a), giving a cross-model realized gain $\Delta_{\text{cross}} = \text{MSE}_{\text{uncond}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{cond,true}}$ and a same-checkpoint gain $\Delta_{\text{within}} = \text{MSE}_{\text{cond,avg}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{cond,true}}$ that removes the cross-model excess-risk confound. We also compute two model-based between-branch spreads from the conditional velocities: a posterior-weighted spread S_{post} (the strict $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ analogue, with $p(k | Y_t)$ a CLIP zero-shot posterior (prompt set and softmax temperature in the released code) on the one-step endpoint $\hat{X} = Y_t + (1 - t)v_{\text{uncond}}(Y_t, t)$) and a uniform class spread S_{uni} (a class-steering quantity, not the strict $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$). Writing $v_\theta(Y_t, t, k)$ for the conditional model’s velocity at Y_t under class k ,

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{uni}}(t) &= \mathbb{E}_{Y_t} \left[\frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|} \sum_k \|v_\theta(Y_t, t, k) - \bar{v}\|^2 \right], & \bar{v} &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|} \sum_k v_\theta(Y_t, t, k), \\ S_{\text{post}}(t) &= \mathbb{E}_{Y_t} \left[\sum_k p(k | Y_t) \|v_\theta(Y_t, t, k) - \bar{v}_p\|^2 \right], & \bar{v}_p &= \sum_k p(k | Y_t) v_\theta(Y_t, t, k), \end{aligned}$$

so S_{post} is the posterior-weighted between-branch velocity spread (the strict $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ analogue) and S_{uni} its uniform-weight counterpart. Because label-averaging weights the classes uniformly, Δ_{within} is matched against S_{uni} , while the cross-model gain Δ_{cross} is matched against the posterior-weighted S_{post} .

Results. In the ambiguity window $t \leq 0.5$, the strict posterior-weighted spread S_{post} predicts the realized cross-model conditioning gain Δ_{cross} in both shape and magnitude: the two profiles agree at cosine 0.9999, and the agreement is tight per t : the relative error $|\Delta_{\text{cross}} - S_{\text{post}}|/S_{\text{post}}$ stays at most $\sim 8\%$ (mean $\sim 5\%$) across the window, with mean ratio $\Delta_{\text{cross}}/S_{\text{post}} = 1.05$ (Figure 7b,d). The realized gain Δ_{cross} (a difference of velocity MSEs) and the spread S_{post} (a posterior-weighted velocity scatter) are different functionals of the same conditional model, so their agreement cross-checks the decomposition directly; the within-checkpoint identity of Appendix E independently places the model within a few percent of its population optimum, which accounts for the residual $\Delta_{\text{cross}}/S_{\text{post}}$ gap as measured excess risk. The CLIP-free same-checkpoint pair matches even more directly over the full t -grid: Δ_{within} tracks the uniform spread S_{uni} with cosine 0.9988 and mean ratio 1.14 (Figure 7c).

Both gains are large near the noise end and decay monotonically; S_{post} falls to near zero by the data end (0.38 at $t = 0.95$ from 37.7 at $t = 0.05$), the expected behavior of the strict $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ as the branch posterior commits. Near the data end the raw cross-model gain Δ_{cross} turns slightly negative (Remark 3): the two checkpoints’ approximation errors $\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_c$ dominate where the true gain has vanished, while S_{post} does not. This makes $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ a more reliable guide to where conditioning helps than the raw MSE difference. An independent estimate of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ (E7a), taken directly from the velocity scatter and using none of the conditional model’s own velocities, recovers the Δ_{cross} t -profile in shape once the bandwidth resolves the ten-way branch posterior (cosine 0.91 to 0.96 at $k \gtrsim 200$; profile recovery is set by the neighbors-per-branch ratio $k/|\mathcal{K}|$, the same resolution requirement as

the model-free $K=10$ audit, Appendix E.2). The full per- t table is Table 5 in Appendix E. The payoff is a velocity-MSE quantity in the model’s pixel velocity space, with S_{post} drawing on a CLIP posterior only for the posterior weights and the within-checkpoint result (Δ_{within} vs S_{uni}) staying CLIP-free.

Robustness across checkpoints and couplings. Two checks extend the real-data results across training amounts and across couplings (Appendix F, Figure 18). The E5 real-path audit keeps its ambiguity-to-commitment shape and proxy-recovery window across the 10k, 30k, and 50k checkpoints of the same unconditional model. Training the matched label-free twins for C_1 and C_3^∞ extends the strict cross-model S_{post} payoff beyond C_0 : with each model evaluated in-distribution, the strict $\Delta_{\text{cross}}/S_{\text{post}}$ ratio is 1.09 (C_1) and 1.10 (C_3^∞) with cosine at least 0.9998, matching the C_0 value 1.05, so the posterior-weighted between-branch spread predicts the realized conditioning gain across all three couplings.

9.5 Validated predictions

Throughout, a *Proposition* is a proved statement and a *Prediction* is a consequence of one tested in our controlled settings. BVD yields two controlled predictions tested in our toy oracles.

- **Prediction 1 (label correctness alone is insufficient).** A coupling can satisfy $\mathbb{P}(K_X=C)=1$ and zero conditional branch entropy while retaining high conditional semantic-coordinate velocity ambiguity, if it is geometrically random within each condition. This prediction targets random within-condition pairing such as our C_2 baseline; class-conditional minibatch OT-CFM performs within-class geometric matching, and its strong empirical behavior is reflected by the C_3^∞ blocked-OT row in Table 1. The E3 C_2 row in Table 1 validates the prediction directly: it has zero mismatch and zero conditional branch entropy, yet retains high semantic-coordinate velocity ambiguity (the per-coupling comparison is in the E3 Results above).
- **Prediction 2 (three layers).** Our (D_G, a, σ_s) geometry-semantics scaling sweep (E3c, §B.1) clarifies that the original “Euclidean OT behaves like geometry-only OT under a weak semantic coordinate” framing conflated three distinct effects. We restate Prediction 2 as three sub-predictions.

Prediction 2a (condition-blind mismatch). When an external condition C is independent of the source variables used by the coupling and is balanced (uniform on its $|\mathcal{K}|$ values), a condition-blind Euclidean OT cannot recover $K_X=C$; its mismatch rate remains at the random baseline. This is formalized at the population level by Proposition 9 and is validated by the E3 C_1 and C_4 rows in Table 1 and across the entire E3c scaling sweep (Appendix B.1).

Prediction 2b (metric semantic alignment). Even when condition-blind, Euclidean OT uses the semantic coordinate in its cost and induces positive semantic endpoint correlation $\rho_S := \text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S) > 0$, which reduces semantic-coordinate velocity ambiguity $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S$ relative to geometry-only OT. The strength of this effect varies smoothly with the geometry-to-semantics scale, calibrated quantitatively by the E3c sweep (§B.1) at fixed σ_s , with ρ_S as the measured directional mechanism.

Prediction 2c (semantic-cost identity recovery, λ -dependent). For fixed λ , semantic-cost OT $C_3@ \lambda$ with *Hungarian assignment* has a phase boundary: at small λ its mismatch stays

high, and a large enough λ recovers identity at every tested cell, including the deepest low-SNR corner. At fixed λ , recovery is governed by the scale match between the semantic penalty and the geometry-induced assignment margins. A row-wise assignment-margin diagnostic that predicts and quantifies this boundary is given in Remark 12 (Appendix B.1).

9.6 Reproducibility and sensitivity analysis

Reproducibility. All results and figures are regenerated end-to-end by the released code on commodity hardware: the toy oracles are CPU-only, and a single GPU suffices for the CIFAR-10 CLIP-feature experiments (E5 and E5a, including the unconditional Flow-Matching E5 audits, the trained-checkpoint E7 payoff, and the E5b bandwidth and E7a independent-estimate checks), the E4 MLP, and the reflow training. External dependencies are the CLIP ViT-B/32 checkpoint and the Python Optimal Transport (POT) library (Sinkhorn appendix); Python, PyTorch, NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn, FAISS, POT, and plotting libraries are version-pinned in `requirements.txt`. Seed lists: E1/E2/E3a single seed 0 (Monte-Carlo verification against analytic curves, with an E2 3-seed addendum); E3b $\{0, 1, 2\}$; E3 $\{0, \dots, 9\}$; E3c 5 seeds per cell from $\{0, \dots, 4\}$; E6 paired train seeds $\{0, \dots, 4\}$ and sample seeds $\{100, \dots, 104\}$ (trained MLP and held-out RK4 pool seeded separately); E4 3 seeds per (t, width) cell from $\{0, 1, 2\}$; E5 model-grounded real-path audit 5 seeds from $\{0, \dots, 4\}$ (resamples data and noise at a fixed model; the E5 model-free feature audit is the E5b row below), E5a 3 seeds from $\{0, 1, 2\}$; E5b 3 seeds from $\{0, 1, 2\}$ with six null partitions ($N = 8000$); E7 and the E7a independent estimate 3 seeds from $\{0, 1, 2\}$ ($N = 2000$), with the E7a $N = 4000$ rows over 2 seeds $\{0, 1\}$. All code, synthetic-data generators, and figure-generation scripts are released in the repository linked in the introduction; the toy experiments use no external data, and the CIFAR-10 and CLIP inputs of E5/E7 are public. The trained CIFAR Flow-Matching checkpoints are available from the authors on request, with the training code and configurations needed to reproduce them in the repository. The final commit hash will be inserted at submission time.

Sensitivity sweeps. The reported numbers throughout the paper use $\lambda = 10$ for the C_3 family and $k = 80$ for the k NN bandwidth. We report three post-hoc sensitivity sweeps around these choices, the bandwidth sweep $k \in \{30, 80, 200\}$ (Appendix I, Tables 9 and 10), the λ sweep, and the Sinkhorn- ε sweep, each chosen wide enough to bracket the regime where the qualitative ordering of couplings could conceivably reverse; the ordering holds within every sweep we report.

10 Discussion

Significance of the decomposition. The conditional-velocity-variance floor of a single-valued field was already known to exist and to depend on the coupling, but it was a single scalar. BVD shows the floor has semantic structure: splitting it over a branch variable separates between-branch switching, which a change of coupling or an explicit per-branch field can remove, from within-branch local uncertainty, the residual that remains after conditioning on the branch. Both are population floors for their respective single-valued fields; model capacity reduces a model’s excess error above them, not the floors themselves. This replaces a qualitative design question, whether relabeling or recoupling will help, with a measured quantity: the switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}} = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}/\mathcal{A}_v$ reports,

before any retraining, how much of the floor a branch-aware intervention can reach. The same quantity appears on both sides of the score/velocity correspondence, equaling a Fisher information of the branch posterior on the diffusion side (Theorem 4). On a trained CIFAR model the between-branch term predicts the velocity-MSE that per-branch conditioning recovers, matching its profile at cosine 0.9999 and, through the strict posterior-weighted spread, its magnitude to within about ten percent (Proposition 1). Beyond describing the floor, the between-branch term forecasts the profile of the conditioning payoff before the conditional model is built, with the calibrated magnitude read from a trained conditional model (§9.4).

What the diagnostic delivers. Three uses follow. First, the floor is an absolute reference for a trained field’s loss: because a well-trained field saturates it (E4, Appendix B), the gap between a model’s per-time velocity-MSE and the floor reads as excess risk, so training health can be gauged against a known target instead of estimated from a large held-out set. Second, the switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}(t)$ localizes where a single-valued field is most strained: the high- R_{switch} regions are where incompatible branch directions are averaged most strongly, and E6 shows recoupling reduces between-branch variance most in those regions. Third, R_{switch} predicts whether a coupling change or per-branch conditioning will pay off before either is built, with proved limits on what a coupling can recover (Propositions 9, 11). The diagnostic is partition-relative: given a branch variable, the floor-saturation calibration established in controlled settings carries to large models in which that variable stays faithful at scale.

Implications for existing techniques. Established techniques act on different surfaces of the pipeline, and BVD gives a common readout for which surface moves the branch-decomposed floor. It applies most directly to path and coupling design, the surface our experiments target: an effective coupling must lower both transport cost and between-branch switching, which is why label correctness alone (C_2) leaves a positive floor while semantic-cost matching (C_3) reaches the Pareto frontier. Class-conditional minibatch OT-CFM is recovered as the $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ limit of that family (the C_3^∞ row of Table 1). As a concrete instance of this readout, one reflow iteration on the four-mode toy removes between-branch variance precisely where the initial coupling’s switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}(t)$ is highest (E6, Appendix C), so the split localizes where recoupling acts and not only whether it will help. This first-iteration locality is the empirical half of Conjecture 1 (§10), whose multi-step form is stated there as an open extension. Conditioning the field on a branch (a per-branch or mixture-of-experts head) recovers a within-branch velocity below the floor, the gain being exactly $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ under an oracle branch variable (Assumption 1) and a lower bound on the oracle gain when the proxy is a coarsening of the oracle partition (Proposition 2). For loss weighting, target preconditioning, distillation, and sampling-time guidance, BVD supplies the readout that tells them apart: reading $\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ before setting a Min-SNR schedule separates the part of the error that capacity can reduce from the part it cannot. On any surface, the split can check whether a reported mid-SNR gain lowers the floor itself or only reduces the excess error above an unchanged floor.

Validated setting and reach. The evidence spans two regimes. Controlled closed-form oracles verify the decomposition’s predictions by construction, confirming the analytic curves, and real CIFAR-10 results read a velocity-MSE diagnostic in CLIP feature space across trained CIFAR Flow-Matching checkpoints spanning three couplings and three training amounts, with resampling

over data and noise at each fixed model. Three directions carry the diagnostics further: detecting coupling differences on real data, relating the velocity-MSE signal to sample quality and FID, and extending single-step reflow locality to multi-step convergence and to large, weakly-semantic settings. These directions share a prerequisite, a branch variable that stays faithful at scale, and constructing one for large image and language models is the main practical step toward deployment there.

Open questions. Two extrapolations are worth stating as falsifiable conjectures. *Conjecture 1 (reflow locality)*: one Rectified-Flow reflow iteration reduces $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ with its between-branch reduction concentrated where the initial coupling has high $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}(t)$; the first-iteration form passes its falsification criteria (Spearman > 0 and a positive top-25/bottom-25 band contrast) on the four-mode toy (E6, Appendix C), and multi-step convergence is the open extension. *Conjecture 2 (diagnostic / guidance overlap)*: the window flagged by $H_K(t)$ and $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ overlaps the band where classifier-free guidance is most effective, both being downstream of the same posterior-ambiguity regime; testing it needs the diagnostic run on a held-out subset with a validated branch variable.

Appendix A Proofs

A.1 Proof of Proposition 2

Fix $Y = y$ and write $M' = \mathbb{E}[U \mid Y = y, K']$, $M = \mathbb{E}[U \mid Y = y, K]$. Since $K = f(K')$, the tower rule gives $M = \mathbb{E}[M' \mid Y = y, K]$. The law of total covariance applied to M' conditionally on $Y = y$ with intermediate variable K yields

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov}(M' \mid Y = y) &= \text{Cov}(\mathbb{E}[M' \mid Y, K] \mid Y = y) + \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(M' \mid Y, K) \mid Y = y] \\ &= \text{Cov}(M \mid Y = y) + \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(M' \mid Y, K) \mid Y = y]. \end{aligned}$$

Taking trace and expectation over Y gives $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K(t) + \Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t)$ with $\Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t) \geq 0$. For the within-branch identity, apply the law of total covariance to U conditionally on (Y, K) with sub- σ -algebra $\sigma(K')$. Because $K = f(K')$, $\sigma(Y, K, K') = \sigma(Y, K')$, so $\mathbb{E}[U \mid Y, K, K'] = M'$ and $\text{Cov}(U \mid Y, K, K') = \text{Cov}(U \mid Y, K')$; hence $\text{Cov}(U \mid Y, K) = \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(U \mid Y, K') \mid Y, K] + \text{Cov}(M' \mid Y, K)$. Trace, expectation over K given Y , and over Y gives $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^{K'}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^K(t) + \Delta_{K' \rightarrow K}(t)$; the totals therefore coincide. The switching-ratio bound follows directly: the numerator $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'}(t) \geq \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K(t)$ by the previous display, while the denominator $\mathcal{A}_v(t) + \epsilon_0$ is invariant under the choice of branch variable, so $R_{\text{switch}}^{K'}(t) \geq R_{\text{switch}}^K(t)$. \blacksquare

A.2 Proof of Proposition 3

The functional $B_q(y) := \text{Tr Cov}_{K \sim q}(m_K(y)) = \sum_k q_k \|m_k(y)\|^2 - \|\sum_k q_k m_k(y)\|^2$ is invariant under a common translation $m_k(y) \mapsto m_k(y) - c(y)$ for any $\sigma(Y)$ -measurable c . For any fixed translation $c(y)$ and writing $\tilde{m}_k = m_k - c$ with $A(y) := \max_k \|\tilde{m}_k(y)\|$: the first term satisfies $|\sum_k (r_k - \hat{r}_k) \|\tilde{m}_k\|^2| \leq A^2 \|r - \hat{r}\|_1$; for the second, $\|\sum_k (r_k - \hat{r}_k) \tilde{m}_k\| \leq A \|r - \hat{r}\|_1$, so $|\|\tilde{\mu}_r\|^2 - \|\tilde{\mu}_{\hat{r}}\|^2| \leq 2A^2 \|r - \hat{r}\|_1$. Combining gives $|B_r(y) - B_{\hat{r}}(y)| \leq 3A(y)^2 \|r(y) - \hat{r}(y)\|_1$. Optimizing $c(y)$ pointwise sends $A(y) \rightarrow R(y)$, giving the pointwise form; averaging over Y and applying $R(y) \leq \bar{R}$ gives (28); further bounding $R(y) \leq \max_k \|m_k(y)\| \leq M$ recovers the global- M corollary. \blacksquare

A.3 Proof of Theorem 4

By the product rule applied to $s_t(x) = \sum_k r_k(x, t) s_{t,k}(x)$, for any perturbation $h \in \mathbb{R}^d$,

$$Ds_t(x)h = \sum_k r_k(x, t) Ds_{t,k}(x)h + \sum_k s_{t,k}(x) \langle \nabla_x r_k(x, t), h \rangle.$$

Differentiating $r_k = \pi_k p_{t,k}/p_t$ and using Theorem 2 yields $\nabla_x r_k = r_k(s_{t,k} - s_t)$. Substituting into the second term,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_k s_{t,k} \langle \nabla_x r_k, h \rangle &= \sum_k r_k s_{t,k} \langle s_{t,k} - s_t, h \rangle \\ &= \sum_k r_k (s_{t,k} - s_t) \langle s_{t,k} - s_t, h \rangle + s_t \sum_k r_k \langle s_{t,k} - s_t, h \rangle \\ &= \sum_k r_k (s_{t,k} - s_t) \langle s_{t,k} - s_t, h \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

where the cross term in the second line vanishes because $\sum_k r_k s_{t,k} = s_t$ by Theorem 2, so $\sum_k r_k (s_{t,k} - s_t) = s_t - s_t = 0$. The displayed linear map is $h \mapsto \text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K})h$ with $\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}) = \sum_k r_k (s_{t,k} - s_t)(s_{t,k} - s_t)^\top$; since h is arbitrary, the matrix identity for $Ds_t(x)$ follows. ■

A.4 Proof of Corollary 2

Let $w_k(x, t) = s_{t,k}(x) - s_t(x)$. By definition of s_t , $\sum_k r_k w_k = 0$, so the vectors $\{w_k : r_k > 0\}$ are linearly dependent and span at most $|\mathcal{K}_{\text{supp}}(x, t)| - 1$ dimensions. The covariance matrix $\text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}) = \sum_k r_k w_k w_k^\top$ is positive semidefinite with rank equal to the dimension of $\text{span}\{w_k : r_k > 0\}$, which is bounded by both d and $|\mathcal{K}_{\text{supp}}| - 1$. For binary $|\mathcal{K}| = 2$, $|\mathcal{K}_{\text{supp}}| \leq 2$, so the bound is 1; substituting $w_\pm = \pm r_\mp (s_{t,+} - s_{t,-})$ recovers the explicit binary form. ■

A.5 Proof of Corollary 4

From $r_k(x, t) = \pi_k p_{t,k}(x)/p_t(x)$, taking $\nabla_x \log$ gives $\nabla_x \log r_k(x, t) = s_{t,k}(x) - s_t(x)$ (using $s_{t,k} = \nabla_x \log p_{t,k}$ and $s_t = \nabla_x \log p_t$). The matrix identity then follows by substitution:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}) &= \sum_k r_k (s_{t,k} - s_t)(s_{t,k} - s_t)^\top = \sum_k r_k (\nabla_x \log r_k)(\nabla_x \log r_k)^\top \\ &= \sum_k \frac{\nabla_x r_k \nabla_x r_k^\top}{r_k}. \end{aligned}$$

The trace identity is the trace of this matrix identity. For the entropy-gradient bound, $\sum_k \nabla_x r_k = \nabla_x \sum_k r_k = 0$. Hence $\nabla_x H = -\sum_k \log r_k \nabla_x r_k$, and adding $H \cdot \sum_k \nabla_x r_k = 0$ rewrites this as $\nabla_x H = -\sum_k (\log r_k + H) \nabla_x r_k$, which is the centered form needed for Cauchy-Schwarz. Applying Cauchy-Schwarz on the K -randomization with weights r_k yields

$$\|\nabla_x H\|^2 \leq \left(\sum_k r_k (\log r_k + H)^2 \right) \left(\sum_k r_k \|\nabla_x \log r_k\|^2 \right) = \text{Var}_{K|x,t}(\log r_K) \cdot \text{Tr Cov}_{K|x,t}(s_{t,K}).$$

■

A.6 Proof of Proposition 10

The marginals factor across the two blocks, $\mu = \mu_G \otimes \mu_S$ and $\nu = \nu_G \otimes \nu_S$, and the cost is separable, so the product of the per-block optimal plans $\pi_G^* \otimes \pi_S^*$ has the correct marginals and total cost $\text{OT}_G + \text{OT}_S$; conversely the two block marginals of any plan are couplings of (μ_G, ν_G) and (μ_S, ν_S) , so its cost is at least $\text{OT}_G + \text{OT}_S$, and the product plan is optimal. The semantic factor π_S^* is the one-dimensional optimal coupling for the convex cost $(z_S - x_S)^2$, that is, the monotone rearrangement $X_S = F_{\nu_S}^{-1}(F_{\mu_S}(Z_S))$, whose comonotone pairing gives $\text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S) > 0$ unless the quantile map is constant. For C_4 the cost reads only the geometry block, so the optimal plan is measurable with respect to (Z_G, X_G) ; the semantic value of the paired target is independent of its geometry and hence of Z_S , giving (Z_S, X_S) independent and $\rho_S = 0$. ■

A.7 Proof of Proposition 11

Conditionally on C , (Z_S, X_S) are independent Gaussian, so $(U_S, Y_t^S) \mid C$ is bivariate Gaussian with $\text{Var}(U_S \mid C) = 1 + \sigma_s^2$, $\text{Var}(Y_t^S \mid C) = (1 - t)^2 + t^2\sigma_s^2$, and $\text{Cov}(U_S, Y_t^S \mid C) = t\sigma_s^2 - (1 - t)$. The bivariate Gaussian conditional-variance identity gives the displayed closed form. Strict positivity follows from positive-definiteness of the within-condition covariance matrix, whose determinant expands as $(1 + \sigma_s^2)((1 - t)^2 + t^2\sigma_s^2) - (t\sigma_s^2 - (1 - t))^2 = \sigma_s^2(t + (1 - t))^2 = \sigma_s^2 > 0$. Independence from a follows because a enters only through means, which drop out of conditional variances. $\mathbb{P}(K_X = C) = 1$ holds by the C_2 construction. The endpoint values follow by direct substitution. For t_* : set the derivative of the subtracted term $f(t) := (t\sigma_s^2 - (1 - t))^2 / ((1 - t)^2 + t^2\sigma_s^2)$ to zero; the numerator $t\sigma_s^2 - (1 - t) = (1 + \sigma_s^2)t - 1$ vanishes at $t_* = 1/(1 + \sigma_s^2)$, which gives the global minimum of f (and hence the maximum of Var) on $[0, 1]$ with value $f(t_*) = 0$ and $\text{Var}(U_S \mid Y_{t_*}^S, C) = 1 + \sigma_s^2$. ■

A.8 Proof of Proposition 12

U_S and $Y_{1/2}^S$ are jointly Gaussian, so $\text{Var}(U_S \mid Y_{1/2}^S) = \text{Var}(U_S) [1 - \text{Corr}(U_S, Y_{1/2}^S)^2]$ is constant in the conditioning value, and since $\mathbb{E}U_S = 0$, $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2}) = \text{Var}(U_S \mid Y_{1/2}^S) / \mathbb{E}[U_S^2] = 1 - \text{Corr}(U_S, Y_{1/2}^S)^2$. Now $\text{Cov}(U_S, Y_{1/2}^S) = \frac{1}{2}(\text{Var}(X_S) - \text{Var}(Z_S)) = \frac{q-1}{2}$ (independent of ρ_S), $\text{Var}(U_S) = q + 1 - 2\rho_S\sqrt{q}$, and $\text{Var}(Y_{1/2}^S) = \frac{1}{4}(1 + q + 2\rho_S\sqrt{q})$, so $\text{Corr}(U_S, Y_{1/2}^S)^2 = (q - 1)^2 / [(q + 1)^2 - 4\rho_S^2q]$. The denominator equals $(q - 1)^2 + 4q(1 - \rho_S^2)$, hence positive for $|\rho_S| \leq 1$ and $q \neq 1$ and strictly decreasing in $|\rho_S|$, so $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2})$ strictly decreases in $|\rho_S|$. ■

Appendix B Calibration and control experiments

These experiments calibrate and stress the diagnostic alongside the four headline results in the main text. The E3c geometry-semantics scaling sweep extends the E3 coupling mechanism (§9.2); E1 is a diffusion-side analytic oracle and E4 checks that a trained MLP saturates the oracle floor; E3a and E3b are geometry-aligned positive controls, with E3b also providing the machine-precision branch-refinement check. Each is reproducible from the released code.

Figure 8: Geometry-semantics scaling sweep (E3c), ρ_S mechanism: semantic endpoint correlation $\rho_S = \text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S)$ explains the C_1 vs C_4 gap. (a) ρ_S vs ℓSNR per coupling. C_0 and C_4 sit at $\rho_S \approx 0$, C_1 stays positive at $\rho_S \in [+0.27, +0.89]$, and $C_3@10$ is comparable. (b) $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2}|C)$ vs ρ_S across all 100 (cell, coupling) points, with the empirical monotone reference $y = 1 - \rho_S$.

B.1 Geometry-semantics scaling sweep over (D_G, a, σ_s) around the E3 cell (E3c)

This subsection extends the single-cell E3 result to a coverage grid in (D_G, a, σ_s) , with the goal of separating three effects that the E3 summary conflated: condition-blind mismatch (Prediction 2a), metric semantic alignment via ρ_S (Prediction 2b), and semantic-cost identity recovery (Prediction 2c). Throughout this subsection we use the geometry-to-semantics scale $\ell\text{SNR} := \log_{10}(a^2/(D_G\sigma_s^2))$, the scale referred to qualitatively in Prediction 2b.

Setup. We extend the headline E3 cell ($D_G=32, a=0.5, \sigma_s=1$) to a 5×5 (D_G, a) heatmap at fixed $\sigma_s=1$, sweeping $D_G \in \{8, 16, 32, 64, 128\}$ and $a \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$ with $N=10,000$ per cell, 5 seeds, $k=80, t=0.5$. Three satellite checks sit alongside, all on the four grid corners and the center: a λ sweep at these five cells with $\lambda \in \{1, 10, 100\}$; a σ_s sanity check at the four corner cells with $\sigma_s \in \{0.5, 2.0\}$; and a t -profile sentinel at the same five cells across $t \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9\}$. The grid center $(32, 0.5, 1)$ coincides with the headline E3 cell; at that shared cell the heatmap protocol ($N=10\text{k}, 5$ seeds) agrees with the E3 protocol ($N=20\text{k}, 10$ seeds) on 15 of 16 paired metric comparisons within 2σ of the inter-protocol difference (the remaining metric, $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(C_4)$, differs by 0.011, which still lies within the typical 5-seed spread). The grid is therefore a coverage-focused complement to the E3 precision.

Results: external mismatch (Prediction 2a). Across all 25 cells, C_1 and C_4 mismatch stay at the random baseline (every cell within $[0.494, 0.505]$, maximum per-cell sample SD 0.009 over five seeds, including the highest-SNR corner ($D_G=8, a=2.0$) at $\ell\text{SNR} = -0.30$), exactly as Proposition 9 requires of any condition-blind coupling on a balanced source condition. Prediction 2a (§9.5) thus holds across the entire (D_G, a) grid, with no measurable departure from the theorem-bounded baseline anywhere on it.

Figure 9: Geometry-semantics scaling sweep (E3c), corner λ -sweep: C_3 mismatch and \tilde{A}_v^S as functions of $\lambda \in \{1, 10, 100\}$ at the four grid corners and the center cell. $\lambda=100$ recovers identity (mismatch ≈ 0.017 , the minibatch-Hungarian irreducible error) at every cell, demonstrating the boundary is λ -specific.

Results: coordinate-level alignment via ρ_S (Prediction 2b, mechanism). The semantic endpoint correlation $\rho_S := \text{Corr}(Z_S, X_S)$ is the mechanism scalar that separates C_1 from C_4 on \tilde{A}_v^S . At every cell in the 25-cell grid: $\rho_S(C_0) \approx 0$ (within ± 0.006); $\rho_S(C_4) \approx 0$ (within ± 0.015); $\rho_S(C_1) \in [+0.27, +0.89]$ (always strongly positive); $\rho_S(C_3@10) \in [+0.26, +0.78]$. These per-cell correlations are recomputed by the released E3c code from the raw semantic transport cost through $\rho_S = (1 + q - T_{\text{sem}})/(2\sqrt{q})$. C_1 induces $\rho_S > 0$ across the entire grid, including the deepest low-SNR corner ($D_G=128, a=0.1$) at $\ell\text{SNR} = -4.11$ where $\rho_S(C_1) = +0.27$ (Figure 8(a)). The plot of \tilde{A}_v^S against ρ_S (Figure 8(b)) collapses 100 (cell, coupling) points onto an approximately monotone curve consistent with $y \approx 1 - \rho_S$: a larger positive source-target semantic correlation goes with lower semantic-coordinate ambiguity. On the ℓSNR axis at fixed $\sigma_s=1$, $\tilde{A}_v^S(C_1)$ collapses onto a single-variable logistic curve (midpoint $\hat{\mu} = -0.51$, scale $\hat{s} = 0.45$, residual RMS 0.038). The collapse does *not* extend across σ_s variation: in the σ_s -sweep corner cells with $\sigma_s \in \{0.5, 2.0\}$, $\tilde{A}_v^S(C_1)$ at matched ℓSNR values differs from the $\sigma_s=1$ curve in magnitude by 0.2 to 0.5. The E3c sweep is therefore an empirical calibration at fixed σ_s : the semantic ambiguity depends on the endpoint variance $q = a^2 + \sigma_s^2$ as well as on ρ_S .

Results: semantic-cost coupling boundary (Prediction 2c, λ -dependent). At fixed $\lambda = 10$, C_3 exhibits a phase boundary across the grid: $\tilde{A}_v^S(C_3@10)$ ranges from 0.13 at the highest-SNR corner ($D_G=8, a=2.0$) to 0.92 at the deepest low-SNR corner ($D_G=128, a=0.1$), roughly tracking the $\ell\text{SNR} = -2$ contour. Sweeping $\lambda \in \{1, 10, 100\}$ at the four grid corners and the center cell (Figure 9) shows that $\lambda=100$ recovers identity (mismatch ≈ 0.017 , the minibatch-Hungarian floor) at *every* cell, including the ($D_G=128, a=0.1$) corner where $C_3@10$ still fails. At fixed λ , C_3 recovery is therefore governed by the scale match between the semantic penalty and the geometry assignment margins. We quantify this with the row-wise margin diagnostic in Remark 12.

Remark 12 (Phase boundary as a margin threshold). Define the row-wise margin $g_i := d_i^{\text{same}} - d_i^{\text{diff}}$, the gap between source Z_i 's squared Euclidean distance to its nearest matching-condition target and to its nearest mismatching one, so a source would individually prefer the matching target

once $\lambda > g_i$. The tail mass $\mathbb{P}(g_i > \lambda)$ predicts the post-Hungarian $C_3@ \lambda$ mismatch rate (Pearson correlation 0.97 across 5 cells $\times \{1, 10, 100\}$, near-1 slope, offset 0.00 to +0.16), since Hungarian assignment couples rows globally. A practical recipe follows: choose $\lambda \approx q_{0.9}(g_i)$ to recover identity at most sources without over-penalizing the geometry, with $\lambda \approx D_G \sigma_s^2$ as a first-pass scale estimate. The diagnostic specializes to the Hungarian assignment; a direct Sinkhorn analogue would express the margin through the dual potentials on a row-stochastic plan.

Sensitivity to t . The headline reading at $t = 1/2$ is a canonical crossing slice. A t -profile over five cells shows that under strong semantic separation (high a) $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t)$ peaks near $t \approx 0.1$, where the $t=1/2$ slice is below \max_t by up to 0.39 at the highest- a corner and by under 0.03 at the lower- a cells. We retain $t = 1/2$ as the reporting convention.

B.2 Diffusion-side commitment-window oracle (E1)

Setup. We consider a 1D binary Gaussian diffusion oracle with $m = 2.0$, intrinsic component standard deviation $s = 0.25$, and $N = 200,000$ Monte Carlo samples per noise level. We plot quantities against $\log \text{SNR} = -2 \log \sigma$, the schedule SNR with $\alpha_t \equiv 1$ and σ the diffusion noise standard deviation (the binary mixture carries its own intrinsic component variance s^2 , separate from σ^2 , so this axis does not include the data-variance normalization of §3). The separability ratio $\rho := m^2/(s^2 + \sigma^2)$ is the binary signal-to-total-noise ratio and equals one when $\sigma^2 = m^2 - s^2 = 3.9375$, i.e., at $\log \text{SNR} \approx -1.371$.

Results. Figure 10 shows that branch entropy decreases from $\log 2$ to nearly zero over a middle-SNR band. The entropy transition rate peaks at $\log \text{SNR} \approx -0.92$, while sample-averaged responsibility-switching curvature peaks at $\log \text{SNR} \approx -0.15$. The heuristic $\rho = 1$ marker lies at $\log \text{SNR} \approx -1.37$. These three peak locations are distinct and together define an overlapping commitment window (Figure 10, panel (e)): entropy transition, branch switching, and local curvature measure different aspects of posterior commitment. All three are deterministic functionals of the binary-mixture posterior $r_+(x, t)$ derived in §6.2, so their separation is exact, and the Monte Carlo curves in Figure 10 verify these closed-form distinctions.

B.3 MLP floor saturation (E4)

Setup. We train fixed- t MLPs on a 1D binary Gaussian FM oracle with the same $m = 2.0$, $s = 0.25$ setting, where closed-form $v^*(y, t)$ and $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ are available. The network has 4 hidden layers with SiLU activation; we sweep hidden widths $\{64, 128, 256\}$ and times $t \in \{0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.8\}$ with 3 seeds per (t, width) cell. Training uses AdamW (lr 10^{-3} , weight decay 10^{-4}), batch size 2048, and $N_{\text{train}} = N_{\text{eval}} = 200,000$ paired samples with evaluation on a fresh held-out sample, at a default budget of 5,000 steps with an extended-control run at 15,000 steps.

Results. Figure 11 shows that the held-out loss coincides with the irreducible oracle lower bound $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$, while the approximation error $\|v_\theta - v^*\|^2$ is two to three orders of magnitude smaller. The identity

$$L_{\text{eval}} = \mathbb{E}\|v_\theta - v^*\|^2 + \mathcal{A}_v(t) \tag{52}$$

Figure 10: Diffusion-side commitment-window oracle (E1). Panels (a)-(d): branch entropy $H_K(\sigma)$, entropy transition rate $|dH_K/d\log \text{SNR}|$, responsibility-switching curvature, and Jacobian decomposition. Panel (e): the same indicators normalized per curve, visualizing a shared intermediate-SNR commitment window. Panels (c) and (d) write the per-time scale as $\tau^2 = s^2 + \sigma^2$ (intrinsic component variance plus diffusion noise variance). The three diagnostics have mathematically distinct peak locations (§6.2) and need not coincide; the vertical $\rho = 1$ marker is a useful onset reference but not an exact maximizer.

holds with mean relative residual $\approx 0.025\%$ (median 0.013%, max 0.139%) across 45 runs (5 time slices \times 3 hidden widths \times 3 seeds). Larger networks under a fixed 5k-step budget show slightly larger approximation error; a longer-training control reduces it, confirming under-training as the source. The MLP approaches the oracle floor within estimator accuracy in this controlled setting, with the residual dominated by the same k NN estimator bias that affects the E2 oracle. A within/between decomposition of the oracle $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ (Figure 12) shows early times dominated by between-branch ambiguity, with the within-branch term taking over near $t \approx 0.58$.

Figure 11: MLP floor saturation (E4), fixed- t verification. Eval loss (solid, circle markers) coincides with the irreducible-floor empirical estimate (dotted, triangle markers, the k NN plug-in of $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$); approximation error $\|v_\theta - v^*\|^2$ (dashed, square markers) is much smaller. In each panel, the horizontal gray dotted reference marks the analytic closed-form $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$. The empirical triangles agree with it to within estimator bias, and the eval-loss circles overlap them. The oracle floor is approached within estimator accuracy across the tested 64 to 256 hidden range under the 5k-step budget.

Figure 12: Within/between decomposition of the same binary FM oracle floor $\mathcal{A}_v(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) + \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ (closed form, $m = 2$, $s = 0.25$). (a) The between-branch term $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ dominates near the noise end, and the within-branch term $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t) = s^2/\tau^2(t)$ overtakes it near $t \approx 0.58$, where $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ cross. (b) The switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)/\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ falls through $1/2$ near the same crossing. Here $\tau^2(t)$ is the per-time interpolation variance and s the intrinsic component standard deviation.

B.4 Geometry-aligned positive controls (E3a / E3b)

Setup. We compare independent coupling, minibatch Euclidean OT, branch-aware random pairing, semantic-cost OT, and the hard-blocked C_3^∞ endpoint in two low-dimensional target distributions: a binary mixture on the x -axis (E3a) and a four-mode diagonal/XOR mixture (E3b). Both use minibatch Hungarian OT with batch size 1024 and k NN bandwidth $k = 80$. E3a uses $N = 50,000$ source-target pairs with a single seed; E3b uses $N = 20,000$ with 3 seeds¹, and the same paths are

¹E3b uses 3 seeds because its primary purpose is the deterministic branch-refinement identity check (residual to machine precision; Appendix B.5); the coupling-comparison numbers on the same paired paths inherit this protocol. The headline E3 experiment uses 10 paired seeds and the E3c scaling-sweep and E6 reflow experiments use 5 paired seeds, both for SD estimation on their non-deterministic scalars.

Figure 13: Geometry-aligned positive control, binary target (E3a; $N=50,000$, single seed). (a) normalized full-state ambiguity $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v(t)$, (b) branch entropy $H_K(t) / \log 2$, (c) switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}(t)$, (d) explained-variance complement $1 - R_v^2(t)$ (equal to the normalized floor $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v(t)$). In the variance panels (a) and (d) both geometry-blind couplings (independent C_0 and branch-aware random C_2) stay non-trivial while the OT couplings (C_1 , semantic-cost $C_3 @ \lambda$) collapse to near zero, because branch identity is geometrically aligned with the target modes. In the entropy panel (b) and the switching-ratio panel (c) the independent coupling C_0 carries the non-trivial signal, and the OT couplings add a brief near-noise-end transient in (c).

reused for the branch-refinement identity check in Appendix B.5.

Results. In both geometry-aligned toys, Euclidean OT constructs branch-respecting paths. For the binary target (Figure 13), independent coupling has $\mathcal{A}_v(0.5) = 1.605$ and $R_{\text{switch}}(0.5) = 0.703$, while Euclidean OT reduces them to 0.013 and 0. All semantic-cost OT variants collapse to the Euclidean OT solution because the semantic branches are already geometrically separated. In the four-mode toy (Figure 14), the qualitative pattern is the same and is more pronounced because four modes are available rather than two: independent coupling and branch-aware random pairing both have $\mathcal{A}_v(0.5) \approx 2.6$ and $R_{\text{switch}}(0.5) \approx 0.7$ (the latter 0.716 ± 0.015 for C_0 and 0.665 ± 0.015 for C_2 across 3 seeds), while Euclidean OT and every semantic-cost OT variant including C_3^∞ drive $\mathcal{A}_v(0.5)$ to about 0.02 and $R_{\text{switch}}(0.5)$ to 0 within seed-SD. These are positive controls: OT can remove ambiguity when Euclidean geometry reveals the semantic branch, the finite-sample counterpart of Proposition 8, where a deterministic injective coupling drives $\text{Cov}(U | Y_t)$ to zero.

Figure 14: Geometry-aligned positive control, four-mode target (E3b; $N=20,000$, 3 seeds, $k=80$). (a) $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$, (b) within-branch $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^K(t)$, (c) between-branch $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K(t)$, (d) switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}^K(t)$ (shaded: seed SD). Independent (C_0) and branch-aware random (C_2) pairings leave large within/between ambiguity; every OT variant (C_1 , semantic-cost $C_3@λ$, and the C_3^∞ limit) collapses to near-zero $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ by routing to a nearby target mode.

B.5 Machine-precision confirmation of branch refinement (E3b)

We use the E3b four-mode toy of §9 as a finite-sample numerical check of Proposition 2. The 4-mode XOR target distribution has two natural nested branch variables: the coarse XOR superclass $K \in \{-1, +1\}$ used in the main text, and the fine mode label $K' \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with the deterministic refinement map $f: K' \mapsto K$ given by $\{0, 1\} \mapsto +1$ and $\{2, 3\} \mapsto -1$. The paired paths (Z, X) and the global k NN neighborhoods at each t are held fixed; only the branch label used in the finite-sample within / between decomposition is changed.

Numerical check. On one global k NN graph per t (the same neighbor sets for the coarse K and fine K' decompositions, so the per-anchor identity and the refinement inequality hold exactly rather than in expectation), across 10 couplings, 3 seeds, and the 19-point t -grid ($N = 20,000$, $k = 80$; 570 cells), all four predictions hold at machine precision: the identity residual $|\mathcal{A}_v - \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}} - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}| \leq 1.8 \times 10^{-14}$; \mathcal{A}_v is exactly label-invariant; $\Delta(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'} - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K \geq 0$ exactly in every cell; and the by-difference and direct-sum estimates of Δ agree to 1.8×10^{-15} . The qualitative pattern is also sharp (Figure 15). The largest refinement gaps occur for the two random-pairing couplings, with

Figure 15: Branch-refinement identity check (E3b appendix). Panels (a) and (b): $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K$ (solid blue, coarse XOR) and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'}$ (dashed orange, fine mode) versus t on the same paired paths and the same global k NN neighborhoods; the shaded gap is $\Delta(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'} - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^K \geq 0$ (Proposition 2). C_2 shows a large gap because random pairing within each XOR class hides cross-mode variance inside the within-coarse-class term; C_1 shows essentially no gap because Euclidean OT routes to nearby target modes. Panel (c): summary across all 10 couplings of $\max_t \Delta(t)$ (mean and sample SD over 3 seeds). The two random-pairing couplings C_0 and C_2 dominate; all OT variants (including the hard-blocked C_3^∞ endpoint) leave $\max_t \Delta$ below 0.15 across seeds.

$\max_t \Delta = 8.76 \pm 0.03$ for C_0 and 7.64 ± 0.03 for C_2 (mean \pm sample SD over 3 seeds). C_0 is largest because fully independent pairing mixes all four modes, so refining from the two XOR classes to four mode labels reveals additional submode switching; C_2 removes the coarse-class mismatch but still leaves long cross-mode paths within each XOR class, which are hidden as within-coarse-class variance under K and revealed as between-mode variance under K' . By contrast, Euclidean OT and the entire semantic-cost OT family route each source to a nearby target mode, so the coarse and fine label assignments are nearly aligned under the coupling, and $\max_t \Delta$ stays below 0.15 across all seeds for every $C_3@\lambda$ value, C_3^∞ , and C_1 , nearly two orders of magnitude below the random-pairing couplings. This is the empirical content of Remark 4: a coarsening proxy under-counts the oracle $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ exactly when the coupling itself does not respect the fine modes, and the gap collapses as the coupling becomes branch-respecting.

Appendix C Experiment E6: first-iteration reflow-locality check on E3b

This appendix tests the first-iteration form of Conjecture 1 (§10): *a single Rectified-Flow reflow iteration should reduce $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$, with its between-branch reduction $\Delta\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{C_0}(t) - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{reflow}}(t)$ concentrated where the initial coupling has high $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}(t)$ (operationalized as Spearman > 0 and a positive top-25%/bot-25 band contrast).* The test target is the E3b 4-mode XOR distribution.

Setup. We train a t -conditioned MLP (width 256, depth 4, Fourier t -embedding of dimension 32, AdamW, learning rate 10^{-3} , weight decay 10^{-4} , batch size 2048, 30,000 steps) with MSE Flow-Matching loss on $N=20,000$ source-target pairs sampled from the independent coupling C_0 on the E3b 4-mode XOR target. After training, we sample fresh source points Z_{new} and integrate the learned velocity field by RK4 with 100 steps from $t=0$ to $t=1$ to obtain reflow endpoints X_{new} . We then label each X_{new} by its nearest mode (giving both the fine label $K' \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and the coarse XOR superclass $K \in \{-1, +1\}$) and recompute the branch decomposition with biased $1/k$ at $k=80$ on the same 19-point t -grid as the main E3b experiment. For baseline comparison we evaluate three side-by-side pipelines on the same paired paths: C_0 (original independent coupling on a held-out pool with seed offset 1000), reflow (the ODE-pushed pairs), and C_1 (Euclidean OT on the same held-out pool). Experiment runs 5 paired seeds (train seeds $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, sample seeds $\{100, 101, 102, 103, 104\}$); we report mean \pm sample SD across seeds.

Results: Conjecture 1 locality. Across 5 paired seeds (Figure 16 and Table 2):

- Reflow removes essentially all of the C_0 ambiguity floor: $\text{removal}_v := \sum_{t \in [0.1, 0.9]} (\mathcal{A}_v^{C_0}(t) - \mathcal{A}_v^{\text{reflow}}(t)) / \sum_t \mathcal{A}_v^{C_0}(t) = 0.998 \pm 0.0001$. The negative-mass diagnostic is exactly zero on every interior t across every seed: reflow never locally increases $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$.
- Under the refined four-mode label K' , the removed floor is overwhelmingly between-mode switching: the interior-integrated share $\sum_t \Delta\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{K'}(t) / \sum_t \Delta\mathcal{A}_v(t) = 0.844 \pm 0.001$, and on the top-25% $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}$ band this rises to 0.979 ± 0.0002 . Under the coarse XOR label K , the interior share is 0.299 ± 0.002 , which matches the saturation reference $\sum_t \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{C_0, K}(t) / \sum_t \mathcal{A}_v^{C_0}(t) = 0.299$. Reflow removes ambiguity in the same proportion that $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{C_0, K}$ occupies the C_0 floor. The factor $0.844/0.299 \approx 2.8$ between fine and coarse shares is branch-refinement monotonicity (Proposition 2) made visible on the removed floor: refining K to K' reveals additional inter-mode switching previously hidden in the coarse within-class term.
- The between-branch reduction $\Delta\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) := \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{C_0}(t) - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{reflow}}(t)$ is monotonically increasing in $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}(t)$ on the 17 interior points of the 19-point t -grid (excluding the two endpoints; locality scatter in Figure 16): Pearson $\rho_P = +0.763 \pm 0.003$ (coarse) and $+0.885 \pm 0.001$ (fine); Spearman = $+0.864 \pm 0.011$ (coarse) and $+0.981 \pm 0.003$ (fine, essentially monotone). The top-25% vs bottom-25% $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}$ band contrast on $\Delta\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ is $+2.77 \pm 0.03$ (coarse). Conjecture 1's first-iteration locality claim therefore holds at both label granularities.

Direction to C_1 baseline. Reflow numerically matches the Euclidean-OT baseline on this geometry-aligned toy: the gap-to- C_1 in interior-integrated \mathcal{A}_v is -0.003 ± 0.0001 (coarse) and

metric	coarse K	fine K'
removal _{v} interior	0.998 ± 0.0001	0.998 ± 0.0001
share interior	0.299 ± 0.002	0.844 ± 0.001
share top-25% R_{switch}	0.618 ± 0.005	0.979 ± 0.0002
saturation reference (interior)	0.299	0.843
Pearson $\rho_P(R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}, \Delta\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}})$	$+0.763 \pm 0.003$	$+0.885 \pm 0.001$
Spearman ρ_{Sp}	$+0.864 \pm 0.011$	$+0.981 \pm 0.003$
top25-bot25 $\Delta\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ diff	$+2.77 \pm 0.03$	–
gap $_{A_v \rightarrow C_1}$ interior	-0.003 ± 0.0001	-0.003 ± 0.0001
negative-mass interior	0 (exact)	0 (exact)

Table 2: Reflow-locality check (E6), headline scalars: mean \pm sample SD across 5 paired seeds. The top25-bot25 band contrast is reported on the coarse label only; the fine-label cell is the no-data dash.

-0.003 ± 0.0001 (fine), where positive values would indicate reflow is worse than C_1 . On the per- t decomposition, reflow and C_1 curves are visually indistinguishable, both sitting at ~ 0.01 - 0.03 across t , well below the C_0 curve at ~ 0.5 - 10 . On the geometry-aligned E3b toy, one reflow iteration recovers the low-ambiguity endpoint, matching the Euclidean-OT baseline (interior-integrated \mathcal{A}_v gap -0.003), without re-solving the OT problem. This *first-iteration, low-dimensional, geometry-aligned* check is consistent with the sharpened Conjecture 1 in §10.

Solver and endpoint calibration. Two auxiliary gates check that the result is not a solver or endpoint artifact. The RK4 solver-convergence gate passes on all five paired seeds, with worst relative change below 2% between 100 and 200 integration steps. The endpoint-calibration gate against the 2D Gaussian target mixture passes on all five paired seeds: mode proportions stay within 0.015 of uniform, per-mode anisotropy is $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\lambda_{\text{min}} = 1.13 \pm 0.07$ and Gaussian W_2 to target is 0.031 ± 0.013 (mean and pooled SD over modes and seeds), with the per-mode radial CDF deviation from the $1 - e^{-r^2/2}$ target reaching 0.028 on two seeds. The locality result above holds across all five seeds. Full per-seed gate values are produced by the released E6 driver.

The locality scatter above summarizes a full per- t decomposition. Figure 17 shows \mathcal{A}_v , $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, and R_{switch} across the t -grid for the independent coupling C_0 , the reflow-pushed coupling, and the Euclidean-OT baseline C_1 , at both the coarse XOR superclass and the fine four-mode granularity: reflow drives $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ far below C_0 across the path and tracks the C_1 baseline in every column, so its R_{switch} follows C_1 rather than C_0 , which keeps switching through mid-path.

Appendix D Real-data branch validation details (E5)

This appendix gives the protocol and full numbers for the real-data validation of §9.3. Both audits use CLIP ViT-B/32 [39] features for the neighborhood and a cardinality null averaged over six random K -way partitions of the same anchors. The model-free feature audit reads three seeds at $N = 8000$ with the bandwidth scaled to hold 20 to 40 neighbors per branch (Appendix D.5); the model-grounded real-path audit reads five seeds at $N = 2000$, holding 40 neighbors per branch ($k = 80$ at $K = 2$, $k = 120$ at $K = 3$). Here a seed varies the held-out data subset and the source-noise draw at a fixed trained model.

Figure 16: Reflow-locality check (E6), locality scatter: $\Delta \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t) := \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{C_0}(t) - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{reflow}}(t)$ vs $R_{\text{switch}}^{C_0}(t)$ on the 19-point t -grid, 5 paired seeds (95 points per panel: 19 grid times \times 5 seeds). The 85 interior points ($t \in [0.1, 0.9]$, 17 per seed) are the solid red dots; the grid endpoints are shown in blue. Linear fit on interior with reported slope. (a) coarse K : Pearson $\rho_P = +0.763$, Spearman $= +0.864$. (b) fine K' : Pearson $\rho_P = +0.885$, Spearman $= +0.981$. The fine-label panel is essentially monotone.

D.1 Branch coarsenings

The oracle CIFAR-10 class is coarsened to $K = 2$ as vehicles {airplane, automobile, ship, truck} versus animals {bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse}; to $K = 3$ as vehicles, {bird, frog}, and {cat, deer, dog, horse}; and $K = 10$ is the full class set. The proxy is unsupervised k -means with the matching number of clusters.

D.2 Model-free feature audit

On $N = 8000$ CLIP features per seed, we use a feature-space surrogate velocity $U = X - Z_f$ with $Z_f \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_d/d)$, $d = 512$, interpolant $Y_t = (1 - t)Z_f + tX$, and report the mean over a 13-point t -grid on $[0.05, 0.95]$. The recovery at each cardinality, its dependence on the neighbors-per-branch ratio, and the fixed-bandwidth under-resolution at fine K are reported in Appendix D.5 (Table 4).

D.3 Model-grounded real-path audit

The trained model is a compact unconditional CIFAR-10 Flow-Matching U-Net trained for 50,000 steps with independent (C_0) coupling; we use its EMA weights. On $N = 2000$ held-out CIFAR-10 test images per seed, with real velocity $U = X - Z$, interpolant $Y_t = (1 - t)Z + tX$, and one-step endpoint estimate $\hat{X} = Y_t + (1 - t)v_\theta(Y_t, t)$, we build the neighborhood on $\text{CLIP}(\hat{X})$ and decompose the real U . The proxy is k -means on $\text{CLIP}(X)$. This audit is a model-grounded validation at small cardinality: we read $K = 2$ and $K = 3$ at a matched 40 neighbors per branch ($k = 80$ and $k = 120$), inside the band E5b shows is well resolved (Appendix D.5); the systematic bandwidth-versus-cardinality scaling and the ten-way split are carried by the model-free audit. Table 3 reports the per- t de-biased

Figure 17: Reflow per- t branch decomposition (E6), 5 paired seeds (mean \pm sample SD). Rows: coarse K (XOR superclass) and fine K' (four-mode index). Columns: $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$, $R_{\text{switch}}(t)$ (symmetric-log y for the first three). Curves: C_0 held-out independent coupling, the reflow ODE-pushed coupling, and the C_1 Euclidean-OT baseline. Reflow tracks the C_1 baseline in every column: $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ (and the floor \mathcal{A}_v) fall far below C_0 across the path, while R_{switch} follows C_1 rather than C_0 , which keeps switching through mid-path.

oracle and proxy signals and the recovery ratio at $K = 2$ and $K = 3$, with neighborhood class purity. The de-biased oracle signal is large near the noise end, decays monotonically, crosses zero near $t = 0.5$, and turns negative by $t = 0.6$, the committed regime in which the coarse oracle no longer captures branch divergence. At $K = 2$ the proxy recovery is near one at small t and is reported only where the de-biased oracle denominator stays resolved from zero; at $K = 3$ the small- t recovery sits above one at all five seeds (1.22 ± 0.16 and 1.27 ± 0.13 ; one-sided sign test, $p = 1/32$). We read this genuine excess not as the proxy failing but as the unsupervised grouping concentrating more between-branch signal than the coarse oracle does: the k -means proxy is not a refinement of the dataset classes, so its de-biased signal has no guaranteed bound relative to the oracle’s, and the oracle three-way coarsening of ten classes is only one of several reasonable groupings.

D.4 Endpoint-neighborhood ablation

The model-grounded audit builds the neighborhood on the predicted endpoint $\text{CLIP}(\hat{X})$, which sharpens with t . To separate branch commitment from that sharpening, we rerun the audit with the neighborhood built instead on the true endpoint $\text{CLIP}(X)$ (model-free; both X and $U = X - Z$ are t -independent, so this reading is constant in t). The two constructions give opposite-sign de-biased signals. The true-endpoint neighborhood is class-pure (neighborhood class purity 0.73 ± 0.01), so the oracle labeling leaves almost no between-branch structure while a balanced random partition still manufactures some, giving a strongly negative de-biased signal ($\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}} = -28.5 \pm 1.8$ at $K = 2$,

t	purity	$K = 2$		$K = 3$	
		$\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}}(\text{or})$	recovery	$\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{deb}}(\text{or})$	recovery
0.1	0.132 ± 0.003	$+13.58 \pm 1.88$	0.98 ± 0.03	$+15.39 \pm 1.89$	1.27 ± 0.13
0.2	0.170 ± 0.006	$+9.14 \pm 1.08$	0.91 ± 0.03	$+10.92 \pm 1.30$	1.22 ± 0.16
0.3	0.226 ± 0.008	$+6.66 \pm 1.38$	0.84 ± 0.07	$+8.61 \pm 1.51$	1.11 ± 0.16
0.4	0.289 ± 0.009	$+4.67 \pm 0.96$	0.66 ± 0.15	$+7.00 \pm 1.20$	0.85 ± 0.19
0.5	0.353 ± 0.011	$+0.95 \pm 1.83$	–	$+3.48 \pm 1.67$	–
0.6	0.417 ± 0.010	-5.23 ± 2.53	–	-1.53 ± 2.36	–

Table 3: Model-grounded real-path audit (E5), per- t de-biased oracle $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ and proxy recovery at $K = 2$ and $K = 3$, with neighborhood class purity ($N = 2000$, five seeds, \pm sample SD; both cardinalities read at 40 neighbors per branch, $k = 80$ at $K = 2$ and $k = 120$ at $K = 3$, with purity at $k = 80$). Recovery is reported only where the de-biased oracle denominator is clearly positive; cells where the per-seed ratio straddles zero near the crossing carry the no-data dash.

constant across t). The model-grounded neighborhood instead mixes branches near the noise end (purity rising $0.13 \rightarrow 0.42$) and produces the positive, decaying signal of Table 3. The decaying t -profile therefore appears only for the model’s one-step posterior-mean endpoint, which groups genuinely branch-ambiguous paths, and not for the class-pure true endpoint, consistent with reading the model-grounded audit as the trained model’s branch confusion (§9.3).

D.5 The bandwidth scales with the branch cardinality (E5b)

The de-biased estimator subtracts a cardinality null, the between-branch variance of a random K -partition of the k nearest neighbors. A random partition leaves $\sim k/K$ neighbors per branch, so the spurious between-branch variance it induces scales as K/k : the null shrinks, and the de-biased recovery sharpens, as the neighbors-per-branch ratio k/K grows. A bandwidth adequate at small K is therefore under-resolved at large K , and k must grow with K to hold k/K fixed. Holding $N = 8000$ and the neighbors-per-branch ratio fixed across cardinalities, the ambiguity-window proxy recovery stays within a few percent of one at every granularity, slightly above it at finer K (Table 4): scaling k with K keeps the recovery at $K = 2, 3$, and 10 all close to one, whereas a single fixed bandwidth under-subtracts the null and depresses the recovery at fine K , driving the full-grid de-biased signal below zero at $K = 10$, $k = 80$. The granularity limit is a bandwidth-versus-cardinality budget; scaling k with K restores recovery to near one at every tested cardinality.

neighbors/branch	$K = 2$	$K = 3$	$K = 10$
20	0.997 ($k=40$)	1.002 ($k=60$)	1.063 ($k=200$)
40	1.011 ($k=80$)	1.041 ($k=120$)	1.066 ($k=400$)

Table 4: Unsupervised-proxy recovery of the oracle between-branch signal in the ambiguity window ($t \leq 1/2$), holding the neighbors-per-branch ratio k/K fixed across the branch cardinality ($N = 8000$, 3 seeds, six null partitions).

t	Δ_{cross}	Δ_{within}	S_{uni}	S_{post}
0.05	+39.54 ± 0.48	42.23 ± 0.45	40.89 ± 0.20	37.66 ± 0.31
0.125	+22.96 ± 0.68	27.69 ± 0.87	26.36 ± 0.07	21.83 ± 0.14
0.20	+14.35 ± 0.83	20.22 ± 0.79	18.67 ± 0.03	13.28 ± 0.11
0.275	+9.58 ± 0.51	16.09 ± 0.63	14.82 ± 0.08	8.92 ± 0.05
0.35	+6.85 ± 0.06	13.77 ± 0.35	12.17 ± 0.07	6.36 ± 0.10
0.425	+4.97 ± 0.11	11.86 ± 0.13	10.05 ± 0.05	4.75 ± 0.05
0.50	+3.61 ± 0.32	10.08 ± 0.06	8.38 ± 0.05	3.63 ± 0.04
0.575	+2.45 ± 0.38	8.30 ± 0.07	6.58 ± 0.04	2.67 ± 0.05
0.65	+1.51 ± 0.28	6.67 ± 0.10	5.33 ± 0.03	2.01 ± 0.03
0.725	+0.68 ± 0.17	5.24 ± 0.11	4.13 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.02
0.80	-0.26 ± 0.08	3.82 ± 0.13	3.13 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01
0.875	-1.34 ± 0.15	2.56 ± 0.08	2.34 ± 0.01	0.63 ± 0.01
0.95	-3.49 ± 0.29	1.53 ± 0.04	1.69 ± 0.00	0.38 ± 0.01

Table 5: Branch-conditioning payoff (E7), per- t realized gains and model-based between-branch spreads ($N = 2000$, three seeds, \pm sample SD).

Appendix E Branch-conditioning payoff details (E7)

This appendix collects the full per-time tables and the independent-estimate details behind the E7 payoff experiment (§9.4).

E.1 Per- t realized gains and spreads

Full per- t values for the E7 payoff experiment (§9.4), mean \pm sample SD over three diagnostic seeds, each in velocity-MSE units (summed over the 3072 dimensions). The realized gains are $\Delta_{\text{cross}} = \text{MSE}_{\text{uncond}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{cond,true}}$ (cross-model) and $\Delta_{\text{within}} = \text{MSE}_{\text{cond,avg}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{cond,true}}$ (same checkpoint); S_{uni} and S_{post} are the uniform and posterior-weighted between-branch spreads.

An exact within-checkpoint identity. The label-averaged gain Δ_{within} admits an exact decomposition that separates the conditioning signal from the model’s excess risk. Writing $\bar{v} = \frac{1}{|K|} \sum_k v_\theta(Y_t, t, k)$ for the label-averaged velocity and v_K for the true-class velocity, expanding the two MSEs gives, for any model,

$$\Delta_{\text{within}}(t) = \mathbb{E}_{Y_t} \sum_k r_k(Y_t) \|v_\theta(Y_t, t, k) - \bar{v}\|^2 + 2\mathbb{E}[(U - v_K) \cdot (v_K - \bar{v})],$$

with $r_k(Y_t) = \mathbb{P}(K=k | Y_t)$. The first term is the posterior-weighted spread of the class velocities about their label-average; the second is orthogonal at the population optimum, where $\mathbb{E}[U - v_K | Y_t, K] = 0$. On the trained C_0 checkpoint the first term accounts for Δ_{within} to within 2% at small t and 8% at $t = 0.5$, so the residual cross-term is a direct measurement of the conditional model’s excess risk. That measurement agrees with the two other excess-risk readings in this experiment: the $\sim 5\%$ mean gap $|\Delta_{\text{cross}} - S_{\text{post}}|/S_{\text{post}}$ and the slightly negative Δ_{cross} near the data end (Table 5), both the $\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_c$ term of Remark 3. Three independent estimates of the same excess risk agreeing to a few percent place the conditional model close to its population optimum, which fixes the $\Delta_{\text{within}}/S_{\text{uni}}$ ratio 1.14 as posterior-versus-uniform weighting together with this small measured cross-term, and gives the magnitude reading of §9.4 a direct excess-risk gauge.

E.2 Independent estimate of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ (E7a)

S_{post} is formed from the conditional model’s own class velocities. As an independent check we instead estimate $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ directly from the velocity scatter with the k NN BVD estimator (cardinality-de-biased over the true class on a $\text{CLIP}(\hat{X})$ neighborhood, as in the E5 model-grounded audit), using none of the conditional model’s velocities, and compare it to the realized gain Δ_{cross} . At the default bandwidth $k = 80$, which leaves only about eight neighbors per branch over ten classes, the shape agreement collapses to cosine 0.20, and the cardinality-de-biased estimate over-subtracts its null and turns negative across most of the t -grid, where the population $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ is nonnegative, so the comparison requires $k \gtrsim 200$ (Table 4). Once the bandwidth resolves the branches it recovers the Δ_{cross} t -profile in the ambiguity window (cosine 0.91 to 0.96; Table 6). The magnitude ratio is bandwidth-dependent rather than a single stable factor (0.57 at $N = 2000$, $k = 200$; 0.44 at $N = 4000$, $k = 400$) and sits below one for two distinct reasons that act in the same direction: the cardinality-de-biased estimate retains a positive finite-sample bias and so over-estimates $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$, while the Δ_{cross} it is measured against is the population gain reduced by the conditional model’s excess risk (Remark 3). Shape, not magnitude, is therefore the established claim of this independent check. The shape agreement persists even at an under-resolved bandwidth (the $k = 200$ row at $N = 4000$), where the magnitude ratio has not yet stabilized. The conditioning gain is thus predicted in shape by an estimator independent of the conditional model, while S_{post} remains the calibrated magnitude estimate at ten-way branch granularity.

N	k	neighbors/branch	cosine	ratio $\Delta_{\text{cross}}/\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$
2000	200	20	0.946	0.565
4000	400	40	0.911	0.435
4000	200	20	0.963	–

Table 6: Independent k NN estimate of $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ versus the realized gain Δ_{cross} (ambiguity window $t \leq 1/2$; the $N = 2000$ row over 3 seeds and four null partitions, the $N = 4000$ rows over 2 seeds and three null partitions). At a matched bandwidth (top two rows) the shape matches and the magnitude ratio is bandwidth-dependent; the under-resolved $k = 200$ at $N = 4000$ keeps the shape but its magnitude ratio is uninformative (no-data dash).

Appendix F Robustness checks for E5 and E7

Two robustness checks extend the E5 model-grounded audit (§9.3) and the E7 payoff (§9.4) beyond their single matched checkpoint. The E5 check is forward-pass only on checkpoints already on disk; the E7 extension trains the matched label-free twins for the C_1 and C_3^∞ couplings and is otherwise forward-pass only.

E5 across training amount. We rerun the E5 model-grounded real-path audit ($K = 2$, three diagnostic seeds) on the same unconditional C_0 model at 10k, 30k, and 50k training steps (Table 7). The de-biased between-branch signal stays large and positive near the noise end and decays monotonically toward zero at every checkpoint, crossing the axis within the grid at the 30k and 50k checkpoints, and proxy recovery stays close to one in the ambiguity window ($t \leq 0.3$). More training lowers the mid- t signal and moves the zero crossing earlier, because the trained model produces a

Figure 18: Robustness checks for E5 and E7. (a) the E5 model-grounded real-path de-biased A_{between} stays positive in the ambiguity window and decays toward zero across the 10k, 30k, and 50k checkpoints of the same unconditional model, crossing within the grid at the 30k and 50k checkpoints with the crossing moving earlier as training proceeds. (b) the E7 strict conditioning-gain identity holds across conditional models trained with C_0 , C_1 , and C_3^∞ , each evaluated in-distribution on its own coupling’s velocity targets: the strict ratio $\Delta_{\text{cross}}/S_{\text{post}}$ in the ambiguity window ($t \leq 0.5$) sits near one (dashed line) at every coupling, with the profile cosine annotated. Error bars are diagnostic resampling SD over three seeds, not independent model-training SD.

sharper one-step endpoint. This establishes training-amount stability across the 10k, 30k, and 50k checkpoints.

E7 payoff across couplings. We extend the full E7 payoff to the C_1 and C_3^∞ couplings by training their matched label-free twins, and evaluate each conditional model in-distribution, on the velocity targets of its own coupling (Table 8). The strict cross-model identity holds for all three: the realized gain Δ_{cross} tracks the posterior-weighted spread S_{post} with mean ratio 1.05, 1.09, and 1.10 and cosine at least 0.9998 in the ambiguity window. The CLIP-free within-checkpoint pairing (Δ_{within} versus S_{uni}) matches over the full t -grid as well, with cosine at least 0.9985 and ratio between 1.14 and 1.17. So the posterior-weighted between-branch spread predicts the realized conditioning gain across all three coupling-trained models (C_0 , C_1 , C_3^∞), not only on C_0 .

Appendix G Real-feature proxy-quality and stability checks (E5a)

This appendix reports the real-feature proxy-quality and L^1 -stability checks (E5a), supporting the real-data validation of §9.3.

We run a real-feature version of the proxy diagnostic on CIFAR-10 [27] CLIP ViT-B/32 [39] embeddings, treating the CIFAR-10 class label as an oracle branch variable K_{oracle} and two unsupervised k -means partitions as proxies: $K_{\text{proxy}}^{\text{CLIP}} = k\text{-means}(\text{CLIP}, K=10)$ and a deliberately weaker $K_{\text{proxy}}^{\text{weakRP}} = k\text{-means}(\text{random-projection}(\text{CLIP}, 16), K=10)$. We score proxy quality by Hungarian-matched accuracy (per-cluster labels permuted to maximize agreement with the oracle via Hungarian assignment on the confusion matrix, then standard classification accuracy), and also report nor-

t	de-biased $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$			proxy recovery		
	10k	30k	50k	10k	30k	50k
0.1	+15.11 \pm 1.95	+13.62 \pm 2.49	+12.90 \pm 2.12	1.00	0.98	0.98
0.2	+9.89 \pm 1.33	+9.53 \pm 1.56	+9.10 \pm 1.43	0.99	0.94	0.92
0.3	+7.40 \pm 1.53	+6.64 \pm 1.73	+6.27 \pm 1.80	0.93	0.83	0.82
0.4	+7.02 \pm 0.91	+4.96 \pm 0.87	+4.38 \pm 1.12	0.85	0.71	0.57
0.5	+5.66 \pm 0.25	+2.40 \pm 1.57	+1.54 \pm 1.10	0.71	–	–
0.6	+2.74 \pm 1.30	–2.36 \pm 2.43	–4.20 \pm 2.29	–	–	–

Table 7: E5 model-grounded real-path audit across unconditional training checkpoints: de-biased between-branch signal (velocity-MSE units) and proxy recovery at 10k / 30k / 50k steps ($K = 2$, three seeds, \pm sample SD). Recovery is reported only where the de-biased oracle signal is positive and resolved from zero across seeds; the no-data marker denotes cells where the oracle signal or the recovery ratio is dominated by seed noise.

conditional model	strict ($t \leq 0.5$)		within-checkpoint (full t)	
	$\cos(\Delta_{\text{cross}}, S_{\text{post}})$	ratio	$\cos(\Delta_{\text{within}}, S_{\text{uni}})$	ratio
C_0	0.9999	1.05	0.9988	1.14
C_1	0.9998	1.09	0.9989	1.17
C_3^∞	0.9999	1.10	0.9985	1.15

Table 8: E7 conditioning-gain payoff across coupling-trained models, each evaluated in-distribution on its own coupling’s velocity targets. Left: the strict cross-model identity, cosine and mean ratio between the realized gain Δ_{cross} and the posterior-weighted between-branch spread S_{post} in the ambiguity window ($t \leq 0.5$). Right: the CLIP-free within-checkpoint identity, Δ_{within} versus the uniform class spread S_{uni} over the full t -grid. Cosines are of the seed-averaged curves (three seeds; per-seed cosine SD below 0.002); the C_0 row is the model of §9.4.

malized mutual information (NMI) and the adjusted Rand index (ARI). The CLIP proxy scores accuracy 0.77, NMI 0.74, ARI 0.65 against the oracle, and the weak proxy accuracy 0.62, NMI 0.46, ARI 0.39. Source-target pairs are formed by sampling X as an L2-normalized CLIP feature and $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_d/d)$ at $d = 512$ (scale-matched so $\mathbb{E}\|Z\|^2 \approx \|X\|^2 = 1$); the coupling is C_0 independent; $N = 10,000$ class-stratified (1,000 per class) per seed, three seeds, k NN bandwidth $k = 80$. A superscript $L \in \{\text{oracle}, \text{CLIP}, \text{weakRP}\}$ denotes the corresponding labeling, so $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^L(t)$ and $R_{\text{switch}}^L(t)$ are the between-branch term and switching ratio computed under it. All three label pipelines share the same global k NN graph at each t (setup detailed below).

The high-quality CLIP proxy tracks the oracle $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ curve to within a few percent through the commitment window ($t \leq 1/2$) and to within 1% of the total floor \mathcal{A}_v at every t (Figure 19); because this is the raw curve, read before the cardinality de-biasing of the main E5 reading, the K/k null that forces k to scale with K in E5b does not enter, and the fixed $k = 80$ resolves even the ten-way oracle here. The weak random-projection proxy, by contrast, deviates substantially and changes sign across the path: it is slightly below the oracle in the noise-dominated regime ($t \lesssim 0.4$) and noticeably above the oracle near the data endpoint ($t \gtrsim 0.5$), reaching a relative gap of about 50% to 80%. The total floor $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ is nearly flat between 1.09 and 1.14 across t : the scale-matched features fix the raw surrogate norm $\|U\|^2 = \|X - Z\|^2 \approx 2$ at every t , and \mathcal{A}_v is the local-mean-subtracted part of that norm (about half), so it inherits the same t -independence. What varies sharply with t is the branch composition: the average number of distinct oracle classes in a local k NN neighborhood collapses

Figure 19: Real-feature proxy diagnostic on CIFAR-10 CLIP ViT-B/32 features ($N = 10,000$, three seeds, $k = 80$, $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_d/d)$). (a) $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^L(t)$ under the oracle CIFAR class K_{oracle} , the CLIP k -means proxy $K_{\text{proxy}}^{\text{CLIP}}$, and a weak random-projection proxy $K_{\text{proxy}}^{\text{weakRP}}$: the CLIP proxy tracks the oracle to within a few percent in the commitment window and within 1% of the total floor at every t , while the weak proxy deviates and changes sign across the path. (b) the switching ratio $R_{\text{switch}}^L(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^L / \mathcal{A}_v$ under the same three labels. (c) the total floor $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$, label-independent and nearly flat between 1.09 and 1.14 under scale-matched Z . (d) the branch commitment of k NN neighborhoods: the mean number of distinct oracle classes $|\mathcal{K}_i|(t)$ collapses from about 10 to about 3, with $\mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{K}_i|=10)$ and $\mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{K}_i|=1)$ crossing in the same transition band where $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}$ drops.

from ~ 10 at $t \leq 0.2$ to ~ 3 at $t \geq 0.9$, with the same transition band where $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ drops. This $|\mathcal{K}_i|(t)$ collapse is the real-feature analogue of the E1 commitment window: noise-dominated neighborhoods mix all classes, and class-pure neighborhoods are the data-near regime.

The sign flip has the following mechanism. At small t , where $Y_t \approx Z$ is class-agnostic Gaussian, the k NN graph mixes all branches and proxy quality matters little, so $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{weakRP}}$ sits slightly below the oracle at the cross-coupling seed-SD level. At large t , where neighborhoods become class-pure under the oracle partition, the weak random-projection partition spuriously merges or splits classes that are well separated in CLIP space, over-attributing local variation to between-branch variance, so $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{weakRP}}$ rises above the oracle.

This check supports the oracle/proxy interpretation of the diagnostic on real image features and shows that proxy quality changes the measured branch composition in a t -dependent way: a moderately faithful proxy (CLIP, NMI 0.74) tracks the oracle between-branch curve across the path while a degraded one (weak projection, NMI 0.46) diverges from it in the data-near regime, so the diagnostic is sensitive to proxy quality and a moderately faithful proxy already suffices.

Quantitative summary. At $t = 0.5$ (mean \pm sample SD over three seeds): $\mathcal{A}_v(0.5) = 1.103 \pm 0.001$ (shared across the three labels), $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{oracle}} = 0.113 \pm 0.001$, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{CLIP}} = 0.109 \pm 0.002$ (within 3.2% of the oracle), and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^{\text{weakRP}} = 0.120 \pm 0.001$ (6.4% above); identity residuals $\mathcal{A}_v - \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}^L - \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}^L$ stay below 2×10^{-15} in all 117 (seed, t , L) cells. For the L^1 bound of Proposition 3, holding the oracle partition and per-anchor first moments fixed and perturbing only the local posterior on the observed support ($\hat{r}_{p,i} = (1-p)r_i + pu_{\mathcal{K}_i}$, $p \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5\}$), the base bound holds in all 117 of 117 cells. The global sup-norm form is loose (RHS/LHS ≈ 20 -25 for $t \geq 0.5$, rising to 75-85 at $t \approx 0.05$, dominated by tail anchors with large noise-regime shifts), while the Chebyshev-radius tightening of Remark 5 (which replaces the absolute magnitude $\|m_{i,k}\|^2$ by the centroid radius $\|m_{i,k} - \bar{m}_i\|^2$, cancelling the anchor-specific translation) is ~ 4 -14 uniformly across t (median 7), 3-6 \times tighter.

Appendix H From DDPM to Flow Matching as Release of Path Design

DDPM fixes a Gaussian Markov path and learns a reverse denoising kernel. Score-SDEs pass to continuous time and learn scores along a stochastic path. Probability-flow ODEs represent the same marginals by deterministic transport. Flow Matching begins directly with a path: choose a coupling $(Z, X) \sim \pi$ and an interpolant $Y_t = \psi_t(Z, X)$. DDPM and score-SDE *implicitly* determine the coupling and the interpolant through the choice of forward noising process (the forward kernel induces an independent coupling between data and noise at $t = 1$ and a Gaussian Ornstein-Uhlenbeck interpolant in between), whereas Flow Matching makes both into explicit, separately tunable design knobs. The linear interpolant has an effective VE-style SNR,

$$\frac{Y_t}{t} = X + \frac{1-t}{t}Z, \quad \text{SNR}_{\text{FM}}(t) = \frac{t^2}{(1-t)^2}, \quad (53)$$

while branch ambiguity is set by the coupling and the geometry.

Appendix I Estimator and Implementation Notes

Step-by-step measurement procedure. Given training-style samples $\{(Z_i, X_i, K_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ from a chosen coupling (or, on the diffusion side, $\{(X_i, K_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ from the data distribution, possibly with the conditioning variable C_i), the diagnostics of §8 are computed as follows (the estimator is Algorithm 1).

1. *Choose the branch variable and condition.* K may be the class label, a discretization of layout / pose / style, or a cluster index on a learned representation. If using an external conditioning input C , decide whether it is treated as equal to K or as a separate variable. This choice fixes the meaning of every later metric.
2. *Form intermediate states and velocities.* For a t -grid covering $[t_{\min}, t_{\max}]$ (we use 19 points in $[0.05, 0.95]$), compute $Y_{t,i} = (1-t)Z_i + tX_i$ and $U_i = X_i - Z_i$. For other interpolants ψ_t replace these with $Y_{t,i} = \psi_t(Z_i, X_i)$ and $U_i = \partial_t \psi_t(Z_i, X_i)$; every subsequent step is unchanged.
3. *Estimate $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$.* At each t , estimate the local conditional covariance $\text{Cov}(U \mid Y_t)$ via a k -nearest-neighbor scatter: for each query point $Y_{t,i}$, average the outer product of the centered velocities

$U_j - \bar{u}_i$ (with \bar{u}_i the mean of U over the neighborhood) across its k nearest neighbors in Y_t -space (Algorithm 1). We use $k = 80$ as default, with bandwidth sensitivity reported below. The biased $1/k$ covariance convention makes the within/between decomposition exactly additive.

4. *Estimate $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$ and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$.* Split the neighborhood by branch: $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$ averages the within-branch local scatter (velocities centered on their own branch’s local mean) and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ is the scatter of the per-branch local means $\hat{\mathbb{E}}[U | Y_t, K]$ about the neighborhood mean, the two summing to $\mathcal{A}_v(t)$ by the local law of total covariance (Algorithm 1). If K must be estimated, an off-the-shelf classifier or clustering on X suffices; the bound direction this estimate induces relative to the oracle is given in step 5.
5. *Report $R_{\text{switch}}(t) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)/(\mathcal{A}_v(t) + \epsilon_0)$.* Numerical stability is good for $\mathcal{A}_v(t) \gg \epsilon_0$, which holds in the interior of the t -grid; near the endpoints the ratio may be dominated by floor noise. Note the direction of the bound when K is approximated (step 4): *if the proxy is a coarsening of the oracle branch variable* (i.e., the proxy \hat{K} is a deterministic function of the oracle K , so the oracle refines the proxy), then by Proposition 2 the estimated $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$ upper-bounds the oracle value, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}} = \mathcal{A}_v - \mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}$ is a *lower* bound, and hence R_{switch} is a lower bound on the oracle ratio. For non-nested proxies (e.g., a noisy classifier whose errors are not a refinement of class identity) the direction can fail; in that regime the diagnostic is a comparative tool across couplings or interventions rather than an absolute bound, and proxy quality (classifier accuracy, NMI, ARI, posterior L^1 gap) should be reported alongside the value. A practitioner using this curve under a coarsening proxy can treat the estimated R_{switch} as a conservative read on between-branch dominance.
6. *Compare couplings.* For a fixed pair of marginals, repeat steps 2 through 5 with several couplings of interest (independent, Euclidean OT, condition-aware random, semantic-cost OT at several λ , etc.). The right intervention is the one that lowers the between-branch component $\mathcal{A}_{\text{between}}(t)$ specifically; a coupling that only lowers $\mathcal{A}_{\text{within}}(t)$ is removing within-branch noise rather than averaging incompatible directions.

k NN covariance convention. For within/between decompositions we use a consistent biased covariance convention with denominator k across all three of $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_v(t)$, $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}}(t)$, and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}}(t)$, so that local total covariance decomposes *exactly* into within plus between terms (the algebraic identity $\sum_j (U_j - \bar{U})^2 = \sum_k \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_k} (U_j - \bar{U}^{(k)})^2 + \sum_k n_k (\bar{U}^{(k)} - \bar{U})^2$ within each k NN neighborhood holds pointwise, and is exactly the per-neighborhood decomposition accumulated in Algorithm 1; dividing the same denominator k propagates the additivity to the trace estimates). If an unbiased $1/(k-1)$ convention is mixed with the biased $1/k$ on different terms, the resulting multiplicative residual between $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_v$ and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}} + \hat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}}$ is $k/(k-1)$; for $k = 80$ that is a 1.27% discrepancy, and $k/(k-1)$ is exactly the bias-correction factor used in the E2 verification (§9.1).

Estimator consistency. The local k NN covariance is a standard nonparametric estimator of $\text{Cov}(U | Y_t=y)$. Under the usual conditions for nearest-neighbor regression (Y_t supported on a compact set or with density bounded away from zero on the region of interest, the conditional second moments $\text{Cov}(U | Y_t=y)$ continuous in y , and a bandwidth schedule with $k \rightarrow \infty$ and $k/n \rightarrow 0$), the local plug-in converges in probability to $\text{Cov}(U | Y_t=y)$ pointwise, so after integration over t the estimates $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_v(t)$, $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{within}}(t)$, and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_{\text{between}}(t)$ are consistent for their population counterparts; this follows from standard distribution-free nearest-neighbor regression theory [14]. At the fixed finite k used here the estimates carry the $k/(k-1)$ convention factor above and an $O((k/n)^{2/d})$

smoothing bias, so we rely on bandwidth-sweep stability (Tables 9, 10) rather than asymptotics for the reported orderings. In high-dimensional learned representations the local neighborhood can additionally degrade through hubness, crowding, or representation mismatch, which is why every proxy-based reading is reported alongside its bandwidth sensitivity and proxy-quality metrics rather than taken as an absolute value.

Branch resolution scales with per-branch sample count, not with a particular bandwidth.

Whether the decomposition resolves a K -way split is governed by how many samples of each branch fall in a local neighborhood, not by the absolute bandwidth. At an uncommitted intermediate state the k neighbors are spread across all branches, so the effective per-branch support is on the order of k/K , and it grows toward the data end as neighborhoods become branch-pure. A fixed k therefore resolves coarser splits before finer ones: at $k = 80$ a binary split is well resolved, whereas a ten-way split leaves about eight neighbors per branch, too few to separate the between-branch signal from the cardinality null (E5b), and the same under-resolution is why the model-free estimate in E7a needs $k \gtrsim 200$. This is a resolution property of the estimator, set jointly by N , K , and k : raising the bandwidth or the sample size restores the signal, as the E5b bandwidth-versus-cardinality sweep and the E7a resolution check show. We choose k to give adequate per-branch support at the K of each experiment, and the ordering and shape conclusions hold across the swept bandwidths.

Conditional k NN in E3. Conditional metrics are estimated by building separate k NN graphs within each value of C . This estimates local statistics under a conditional model $v_\theta(Y_t, t, C)$ rather than filtering same- C neighbors after an unconditional query.

Metric convention in E3. The semantic-cost OT assignment minimizes $\|Z - X\|^2 + \lambda \mathbf{1}[C \neq K_X]$, but reported transport costs are raw Euclidean costs after assignment: T_{geom} on nuisance coordinates, T_{sem} on the semantic coordinate, and $T_{\text{full}} = T_{\text{geom}} + T_{\text{sem}}$. The assignment objective is not reported as transport. The exact additive equality $T_{\text{full}} = T_{\text{geom}} + T_{\text{sem}}$ relies on two properties of the E3 construction: (i) the coordinate split $X = [G, S]$ places nuisance and semantic coordinates in mutually *orthogonal* subspaces, and (ii) the squared-Euclidean cost is separable across orthogonal directions. The decomposition therefore extends to any orthogonal rotation of this split, but for semantic features that are not represented as a linearly separable orthogonal subspace (for instance, non-linear semantic embeddings extracted from natural images), the additive identity does not apply and the analogue of T_{sem} would need a representation-dependent definition.

Bandwidth sensitivity of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S$ in E3. Headline E3 numbers use $k=80$. Tables 9 and 10 report $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t=1/2|C)$ and $\max_t \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t|C)$ for $k \in \{30, 80, 200\}$. Absolute values shift by a few percent across this range, but the coupling ordering is stable: C_3^∞ is consistently the lowest, $C_3@ \lambda=30/100$ are close to C_3^∞ in absolute value (the cross-coupling seed-SDs reported in the bandwidth tables are independent, not paired; cf. §9.2 for the paired-difference comparison at $k = 80$), C_0 and C_4 stay highest, and C_1 and C_2 sit between them and the C_3 family, with the ranking identical at every k .

Coupling	$k=30$	$k=80$	$k=200$
C_0 independent	0.964 ± 0.014	0.985 ± 0.013	0.993 ± 0.013
C_1 Euclidean OT	0.823 ± 0.007	0.845 ± 0.007	0.859 ± 0.007
C_2 cond.-aware random	0.861 ± 0.014	0.879 ± 0.013	0.885 ± 0.012
$C_3@λ=1$	0.818 ± 0.008	0.840 ± 0.009	0.855 ± 0.008
$C_3@λ=3$	0.800 ± 0.005	0.821 ± 0.005	0.834 ± 0.005
$C_3@λ=10$	0.710 ± 0.011	0.728 ± 0.012	0.739 ± 0.011
$C_3@λ=30$	0.696 ± 0.010	0.713 ± 0.010	0.724 ± 0.010
$C_3@λ=100$	0.690 ± 0.008	0.708 ± 0.008	0.719 ± 0.008
C_3^∞ blocked OT	0.677 ± 0.008	0.694 ± 0.008	0.705 ± 0.007
C_4 geometry-only OT	0.962 ± 0.011	0.983 ± 0.011	0.991 ± 0.010

Table 9: Bandwidth sensitivity of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t=1/2|C)$ for E3. Mean \pm sample SD over 10 seeds. Coupling ordering is stable across $k \in \{30, 80, 200\}$ even though absolute values shift by a few percent.

Coupling	$k=30$	$k=80$	$k=200$
C_0 independent	0.971 ± 0.015	0.992 ± 0.015	0.999 ± 0.013
C_1 Euclidean OT	0.850 ± 0.008	0.871 ± 0.008	0.884 ± 0.008
C_2 cond.-aware random	0.861 ± 0.014	0.879 ± 0.013	0.885 ± 0.012
$C_3@λ=1$	0.848 ± 0.014	0.870 ± 0.014	0.882 ± 0.013
$C_3@λ=3$	0.822 ± 0.006	0.843 ± 0.007	0.856 ± 0.006
$C_3@λ=10$	0.712 ± 0.011	0.730 ± 0.011	0.742 ± 0.011
$C_3@λ=30$	0.698 ± 0.010	0.715 ± 0.010	0.725 ± 0.010
$C_3@λ=100$	0.692 ± 0.008	0.709 ± 0.007	0.720 ± 0.007
C_3^∞ blocked OT	0.678 ± 0.009	0.695 ± 0.009	0.706 ± 0.008
C_4 geometry-only OT	0.967 ± 0.012	0.988 ± 0.012	0.995 ± 0.011

Table 10: Bandwidth sensitivity of $\max_t \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t|C)$ for E3. Mean \pm sample SD over 10 seeds. Same ordering invariance as Table 9.

Coupling	mismatch	T_{full}	$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2} C)$	$\max_t \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(t C)$	$H(K_X Y_{1/2}, C)/\log 2$
C_1 Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.03$	0.501 ± 0.001	34.64 ± 0.03	0.869 ± 0.009	0.891 ± 0.003	0.968 ± 0.000
C_1 Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.1$	0.498 ± 0.003	47.82 ± 0.08	0.978 ± 0.007	0.982 ± 0.007	0.971 ± 0.000
C_1 Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.3$	0.501 ± 0.002	59.37 ± 0.08	0.984 ± 0.011	0.988 ± 0.008	0.975 ± 0.001
$C_3@λ=10$ Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.03$	0.055 ± 0.001	36.32 ± 0.04	0.766 ± 0.015	0.767 ± 0.015	0.168 ± 0.009
$C_3@λ=10$ Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.1$	0.202 ± 0.003	48.96 ± 0.11	0.931 ± 0.010	0.933 ± 0.011	0.685 ± 0.015
$C_3@λ=10$ Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.3$	0.385 ± 0.002	59.98 ± 0.02	0.986 ± 0.029	0.990 ± 0.027	0.934 ± 0.004
C_4 Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.03$	0.501 ± 0.003	35.29 ± 0.07	0.989 ± 0.009	0.994 ± 0.011	0.981 ± 0.001
C_4 Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.1$	0.500 ± 0.002	47.92 ± 0.06	0.991 ± 0.020	0.995 ± 0.019	0.980 ± 0.001
C_4 Sinkhorn, $\varepsilon=0.3$	0.501 ± 0.001	59.55 ± 0.11	0.976 ± 0.015	0.982 ± 0.014	0.978 ± 0.001
C_1 Euclidean OT (Hungarian)	0.502 ± 0.002	32.75 ± 0.03	0.848 ± 0.006	0.876 ± 0.005	0.966 ± 0.002
$C_3@λ=10$ (Hungarian)	0.042 ± 0.003	34.36 ± 0.03	0.725 ± 0.011	0.727 ± 0.010	0.106 ± 0.012
C_4 geometry-only OT (Hungarian)	0.502 ± 0.005	33.46 ± 0.03	0.992 ± 0.013	0.997 ± 0.012	0.983 ± 0.001

Table 11: Entropy-regularized Sinkhorn vs Hungarian assignments on the E3 conditional-mismatch experiment. All values are mean \pm sample standard deviation over 3 seeds at $N=20,000$, $k=80$. The C_3 Sinkhorn rows use the same $\lambda=10$ semantic penalty before per-batch median cost rescaling. The Hungarian rows shown here are 3-seed companion runs to the Sinkhorn block; the corresponding 10-seed values are in Table 1, and the small numerical differences from there reflect the seed-count change.

Figure 20: Entropy-regularized Sinkhorn vs Hungarian couplings on the E3 conditional-mismatch experiment ($N = 20,000$, 3 seeds, $k = 80$). The legend at the top of the figure applies to panel (a). (a) transport vs semantic ambiguity $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2}|C)$: each coupling family (C_1 Euclidean, $C_3@ \lambda=10$, C_4 geometry-only) at $\epsilon \in \{0.03, 0.1, 0.3\}$ (small markers) and the Hungarian limit (large diamonds); only $C_3@10$ moves toward low ambiguity. (b) mismatch rate $\mathbb{P}(K_X \neq C)$ vs ϵ : Euclidean and geometry-only stay at ≈ 0.5 (condition-blind) at every ϵ , while $C_3@10$ lowers mismatch, approaching the Hungarian limit as ϵ shrinks.

Appendix J Entropy-Regularized Sinkhorn Couplings

We additionally test entropy-regularized Sinkhorn couplings on the E3 conditional-mismatch experiment to check that the Hungarian Pareto ordering reported in the main text is not an artifact of hard assignment. For each minibatch we rescale the cost matrix by its median, compute a Sinkhorn plan with the Python Optimal Transport (POT) library [10] at regularization $\epsilon \in \{0.03, 0.1, 0.3\}$, and sample paired paths by row-stratified sampling: for each source i we draw exactly one target index j_i from the row distribution $P_{ij}/\sum_j P_{ij}$. Each source therefore appears once, while a target may appear multiple times; the empirical fraction of unique targets is $\approx 1 - 1/e \approx 63\%$, matching the theoretical row-stratified-sampling prediction. The C_3 Sinkhorn variant uses the same $\lambda=10$ semantic penalty as in the main text, applied to the raw cost before per-batch median rescaling. We evaluate three base couplings (C_1 , $C_3@ \lambda=10$, C_4) at three values of ϵ , for a total of nine Sinkhorn (coupling, ϵ) cells, each at $N=20,000$ over 3 seeds.

Sinkhorn preserves the Hungarian ordering at every tested ϵ (Figure 20 and Table 11): Euclidean and geometry-only Sinkhorn stay condition-blind (mismatch ≈ 0.5), while only $C_3@ \lambda=10$ Sinkhorn lowers both mismatch and conditional ambiguity. As ϵ decreases it approaches the Hungarian limit (at $\epsilon=0.03$, mismatch 0.055 vs 0.042 and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_v^S(\frac{1}{2}|C)$ 0.766 vs 0.725); larger ϵ diffuses the sampled plan and washes out the semantic-cost signal (mismatch rises to 0.385 at $\epsilon=0.3$), without reaching the 0.5 random-pairing floor. The Hungarian Pareto ordering of Table 1 is therefore not an artifact of hard assignment.

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